

Continuous Integration, Choreographically^{*}

Adrian Francalanza¹, Claudio Antares Mezzina², José Miguel Rojas², Emilio Tuosto²,
and Irek Ulidowski²

¹ University of Malta, Malta adrian.francalanza@um.edu.mt

² University of Leicester, UK emilio@le.ac.uk

Abstract. Continuous Integration (CI) is a widely used software development methodology advocating for the immediate integration of changes to code builds. One solution to the development bottlenecks resulting from frequent builds induced by the methodology is to use parallel/distributed workflows. In addition to the intricacies associated with devising distributed choreographies of test-and-build tasks, these workflows may need to contend with failure and strategies for recovery. In present solutions, the onus of devising such workflows is left to the user who has to describe them in terms of low-level error-prone scripts. We propose a high-level formalism for describing distributed CI workflows imbued with reversible behaviour to support automatic test generation and flakiness detection. We show how executable code is automatically generated from these workflow descriptions with the help of realistic software testing scenarios.

1 Introduction

Continuous Integration (CI) is a development methodology where team members integrate their work into shared repositories frequently. As a result, the volume and frequency of integrations are very high: multiple builds per day as opposed to single weekly or monthly builds [13]. This methodology increases software quality and productivity [29] and is particularly beneficial to large projects where code is written in a cooperative manner since: *a*) it accelerates the detection of bugs due to the high frequency of testing, *b*) it facilitates better fault localisation because new bugs are immediately attributed to the source code that introduced them, and *c*) it expedites the delivery of new software features. CI has been widely adopted in the software industry, especially by big companies such as Google and Facebook [17, 9]. For example, at Google, there are ~17K code commits per day (made by over ~10k developers working on more than ~5K different projects). In turn, these commits trigger ~100 millions of test runs per day. Cloud platforms such as Travis CI, Jenkins, and CircleCI³ provide CI as-a-service and seamlessly integrate in software development platforms like Github.

In spite of many advantages, CI poses several challenges [12, 27]. Specifically, the methodology necessitates tool support to automate its workflows and to assist with decisions such as when to integrate to the master branch and what tests to run for each build. CI also poses challenges for how to speed up the building process: usually, compiling and building a complex software takes several hours [15], which goes against the very idea of continuous integration. Slow builds may also create severe bottlenecks in

^{*} Research supported by the EU H2020 RISE programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 778233.

³ See <https://travis-ci.org/>, <https://jenkins.io/>, and <https://circleci.com/>

the development lifecycle and may cause delays in delivery. One way to speed-up the integration phase, adopted by several CI commercial solutions, is through parallel and distributed testing [15, 24]. In other words, workflows in the building process, called *pipelines*, feature the parallel execution of tasks, possibly on different machines. Since CI pipelines usually consist of tasks that are either independent of each other or require interactions with external services, parallelism and distribution in testing can drastically decrease the total building time⁴. The scripting languages of CI services such as Jenkins and Travis feature mechanisms to support parallel and distributed pipelines. However, they solve the problem of automation and speed-up only partially. A primary limitation of these languages is that they do not provide any support to leverage and control emerging CI-enhancement techniques such as test flakiness detection (FD) [4] and automated test generation (ATG) [5].

Contributions. The main goal of this work is to overcome this lack of support for advanced CI-extensions. The main contributions of this paper are:

- a) We propose a model-driven approach based on choreographies and *controlled reversibility*. We argue that reversibility is a powerful and natural software engineering abstraction to deal with ATG and FD. Indeed, ATG and FD often require to undo or redo the computation of some pipelines depending on some *local* conditions—we evidence this in the two case studies of Section 2. We adopt reversibility-enabling global graphs (ReGs) [14], a choreographic modelling language that features asynchronous message passing, distributed choices and iteration, parallelism and distribution, and a support for computation reversal.
- b) We devise appropriate abstractions and tools that combine declarative mechanisms for reversibility and the *correctness-by-design* approach typical of choreographic framework. Upon a test failure, determining if the test has become flaky remains an open problem and only few recent approaches to do so exist in the literature (e.g., [4]). Detecting flaky tests is particularly hard because these tests produce non-deterministic (unstable) results on the same version of code due to external factors, e.g., access to the file system. Reversibility is achieved in ReGs via *reversion guards* detailed in Section 3. These are predicates that declaratively specify the conditions for a reversing of computation [21, 25, 7, 3]. More precisely, reversion guards are checked at choice and iteration points. When they evaluate to true then the computation may need to be redone or undone in order to explore possible alternative computations. This combination provides an expressive framework for specifying ATG and FD in CI.
- c) We propose the application of this framework to two realistic case studies of CI with FD and ATG. Our model-driven approach enables the automated generation executable code from ReGs. Users can specify CI pipelines by simply defining a ReG model decorated with reversion guards to integrate ATG or FD. This is illustrated in Sections 4 to 6. The abstractions for reversible computation provided by ReGs can be used to describe recovery strategies in a lightweight fashion, since the

⁴ In the case of ZenDesk [15] the total build time dropped from 4 hours to few minutes.

reversible models automatically account for undoing of computation [26, 22]. Here we show how these abstractions are compiled to implement controlled reversibility of distributed iterations, which had not been done before [14]. Section 5 shows how to relax the syntactic restriction on the parallel composition imposed in [14].

Existing CI scripting languages offer some constructs that allow one to “simulate” reversible computations. For instance, Travis supports *timeouts* for failure detection and Jenkins supports *checkpoints* for saving and restarting of pipelines. However, these constructs are designed to handle recovery strategies necessary *when faults occur* in the running environment (e.g., a service becomes unresponsive or unreachable). Also, it is up to the developer to combine these non-trivial mechanisms into a coherent recovery strategy and then to interleave it with the script logic describing the (concurrent) workflow under normal circumstances. In Section 7 we shall describe the advantages of declarative reversibility as compared to mechanisms such as timeouts or checkpoints. Our findings highlight that reversion guards are lighter and more effective than those mechanisms for supporting ATG and FD with those constructs.

The use of ReGs in our approach provides additional benefits in terms of scalability. Unlike the low-level communication mechanisms (such as `ssh`) used by existing CI scripting languages, ReGs are based on asynchronous message-passing which has proven crucial to the scalability of distributed applications. For example, the Erlang and BEAM technologies that we use in our approach power WhatsApp, Facebook, and Basho Riak⁵. Finally, executable code can be automatically generated from ReGs. We spell out how ReGs are compiled into Erlang code that *decouples* the components concerned with the normal (forward) execution from those administering the reversal of the computation. (The generated code is in Appendix A.3.) The decoupling is achieved using Monitor-Oriented Programming [6], whereby monitors observe the execution of forward components and intervene at runtime when reversion guards trigger reversibility. All units of execution are implemented as actors interacting exclusively via asynchronous message passing; this makes our solution more scalable and easier to parallelise and distribute.

2 Case Studies

We consider two CI pipelines [12]. The first workflow involves the flakiness detection and the second concerns automated test generation during the integration phase.

Flaky tests It has been recently argued that keeping flaky tests in integration test suites is worthwhile because they could reveal code defects [23]. They are however handled differently from normal tests: the outcome of a flaky test is typically obtained by aggregating the outcome of multiple executions. We remark that this exacerbates the integration bottleneck problem in CI.

⁵ See <https://goo.gl/eXKng1>, <https://goo.gl/Z1tpgA>, and <http://goo.gl/GK9II3>

Fig. 1. Flaky test pipeline

Yet, recent studies show that certain classes of flaky tests may be detected effectively. For instance, the empirical classification in [23] identifies three categories of flaky tests: *asynch-wait* tests (AWtests), *order-dependency* tests (ODtests), and *concurrency* tests (Ctests).

An AWtest is flaky because its execution makes an asynchronous call and fails to wait for the result of the call to become available. The source of flakiness in ODtests is due to the fact that the outcome of a series of tests depends on the order in which memory is accessed and updated when tests are executed. Finally, Ctests are broadly those tests for which there is no definite way how to resolve their non-deterministic outcomes. AWtests can be rendered deterministic by introducing delays (e.g., calling a waiting routine) and ODtests can be made deterministic by resetting the shared state (e.g., shared memory or files) before executing them. Since these two mitigating strategies can be implemented locally, for simplicity, our example considers only one of them (ODtests) and the more general Ctests.

Fig. 1 depicts our pipeline in the visual representation of ReGs (slightly adapted from [16, 28]). The pipeline involves a testing server T, a machine M running the tests, and a logger server L recording the outcome of each execution. The pipeline consists of a distributed choice which is denoted by the topmost \diamond -labelled node. The first branch is when M sends the message testOD and the second branch is when the message testC is sent by M. T decides locally which message to send, based on a heuristic that the programmer has to provide (e.g., by adopting those proposed in [23]). If T chooses to execute the right-hand side by sending to M the test to check for flakiness (via the message testC), then a common strategy is adopted where the test is executed multiple times (the loop represented by the topmost \diamond -labelled node in right-hand side branch) until a satisfactory aggregate test outcome is obtained. Then, based on the outcome, we ascertain if the test is indeed flaky or it is a potentially fault-revealing test. We note that, neither this branch nor its loop are reversible.

The situation is different in the other branch. After receiving the test suite via the message testOD, the machine M enters a reversible loop: it runs each test according to an execution order (established by M and not specified in the ReG). The outcome of each execution is sent to the logger L to be recorded. Then L evaluates the reversion guard, represented by ϕ_{OD} in Fig. 1, to check if the test outcome is unstable. Hence L decides whether or not to redo the loop. The machine M has an option to run tests in a different order when redoing the loop. Should the test outcome remain unstable after a number of executions, the workflow could even try to reverse the initial choice and attempt the other pipeline for the Ctests. This is achieved using reversion guards on the left-hand side branch of the choice. For simplicity, we do not give guards here and illustrate how reversion of branches works in the next case study.

Test generation Consider the workflow depicted in Fig. 2. The developer D checks out (e.g., `git pull`) the code from the repository R and, after modifying it, makes a commit or pull request to integrate the changes to R. Upon a commit, the testing server T decides how to carry out the code build. If the commit constitutes a *refactoring* of the present code or a *refinement* of an existing functionality, then T farms out an exhaustive

regression testing (i.e., all tests existing in the project⁶) to the machine M (the outer loop of the left-hand side branch in Fig. 2). The machine M iterates through the individual regression unit tests (the inner loop on the left), recording *each* test outcome at a logger L_1 . Upon completion of this test execution phase, two overall outcomes are possible: either some tests fail or all tests pass. The former case indicates a regression has been introduced in the commit and it should be rejected (unless the test is deemed flaky). When all the tests pass, it may indicate an inadequacy in the existing test suites (e.g., insufficient code coverage). In this scenario, the use of automated test generation on the fly [5] can be a suitable alternative to augment the existing regression test suites and to increase the chances of revealing regression faults. This is modelled in Fig. 2 by the message `newTest` sent by the logger L_1 , who decides if test augmentation is needed, to the tester T , who carries out the test generation process. At this point, if new tests have been generated then they are executed by redoing the iteration. Otherwise the branch terminates and the code build is complete.

If the code submitted contains a *new functionality*, the build workflow takes the right-hand side branch in Fig. 2. The testing server T carries out *two tasks* on the dedicated machine M *in parallel*⁷ (represented by the \square -labelled node in Fig. 2). More precisely: *a*) M iteratively verifies that *all* the basic *unit tests* provided by the developer (for the new functionality) are indeed satisfied, reporting every result to the logger L_1 (the loop in the right-hand side parallel thread), while *b*) in parallel, M also selects a series of *integration tests* to ensure that the new functionality is still in harmony with the global system (including third-party components). This is modelled with the loop in the left-hand side thread. The machine M checks these integration tests in sequence and reports to a global logger L_g whether a new integration defect is discovered. Otherwise, M sends the message `stable` when the outcome for the test is the same as the outcome during the previous build. If all unit and integration tests pass in the two threads, the submitted code is integrated with the main build. Test generation could be also triggered here, but for the sake of simplicity we leave this case out of the model.

Although extensive, the decisions taken within this test-generation workflow may be too rigid in practice. For instance, we could monitor for the intermediate outcomes of the exhaustive-test branch and if, after a certain time or number of test executions, we estimate that it would not reveal new defects (in order to justify the extensive resources consumed by exhaustive testing), then we would terminate this branch. In Fig. 2, this is captured by the condition $\phi_{\text{ratio}} \equiv \frac{\text{new_failures}}{\text{new_failures} + \text{old_failures}} \leq \text{threshold}$. When ϕ_{ratio} is satisfied it means that the computation carried out in the left-hand side branch should be reversed and that the rightmost branch is taken instead. Dually, the right-hand side branch is taken when the build contains a new functionality. If the integration tests (represented by the condition ϕ_{new} in Fig. 2) reveal new defects, is worthwhile to reverse the computation and go for the exhaustive testing instead in order to get a better insight of the impact of the defects. Finally, Fig. 2 contains a third reversibility condition, cf. ϕ_{diff} , that monitors whether the current exhaustive testing branch has revealed any new

⁶ Regression test selection or prioritisation techniques may be used at a cost [30].

⁷ In practice, different machines M_1, M_2, \dots can be used to carry out parallel tasks, but we chose here to use the same machine M to keep the exposition simple.

Fig. 2. Visual representation of the pipeline for ATG

defect as compared to those in the previous builds. If it is *not* the case, then it may be wiser to stop wasting resources with this exhaustive testing.

3 Background

Among the many proposals for the specification of distributed workflows, behavioural models based on message-passing have attracted wide interest [20]. We adopt *reversibility-enabling global graphs* (ReGs) [14] that, as discussed later in Sections 4 and 5, *a*) are expressive enough to cover the needs required in CI, *b*) have an intuitive graphical presentation (cf. Section 2), and *c*) are supported by prototype tools for the analysis of the workflow. We provide a source-to-source compiler to generate Erlang executable programs from ReGs. These graphs augment global graphs [28, 16, 10] to express and automate the handling of the coordination associated with reversible computation.

We now review ReGs. Let \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{M} be two disjoint sets of *participants* (ranged over by A, B , etc.) and *messages* (ranged over by m) respectively. A ReG is a term

derivable from the following grammar:

$G ::= A \rightarrow B : m$	(interaction)
$G; G'$	(sequence)
$G \mid G'$	(parallel)
repeat $A\{G \text{ unless } \phi\}$	(iteration)
branch $A\{G_1 \text{ unless } \phi_1 + G_2 \text{ unless } \phi_2\}$	(choice)

An interaction $A \rightarrow B : m$ denotes that participant A sends a message m to B , where we require that $A \neq B$. Note that ReGs abstract away from data: the message m in $A \rightarrow B : m$ should be thought of as (the name of) a data type, not as a value. Although the interpretation of sequential and parallel compositions ($G; G'$ and $G \mid G'$) is straightforward, some explanation is needed for the iteration and choice constructs as they involve *reversion guards*, i.e. conditions to trigger undoing of computation.

The body G in an iteration **repeat** $A\{G \text{ unless } \phi\}$ is repeated until the participant A stops the loop (we require that A is a participant of G). The construct leaves implicit the interactions needed for coordinating all the participants in G to correctly loop or exit the loop. Those interactions are *automatically generated* in the components obtained from the compilation of the workflow. Our iteration construct extends the one in [14] with the **unless** ϕ clause to control the rollback execution. The guard ϕ assigns a condition $\phi(B)$ to *each* participant B of G . The evaluation of $\phi(B)$ is local to B , that is the evaluation of $\phi(B)$ and does not require any communication with other participants. When $\phi(B)$ evaluates to true, the execution of the loop might be rolled back. Hereafter, **unless** ϕ is omitted when $\phi(B) = \text{false}$ for all B in the domain of ϕ . The choice construct **branch** $A\{G_1 \text{ unless } \phi_1 + G_2 \text{ unless } \phi_2\}$ specifies a distributed (non-deterministic) choice⁸ between workflows G_1 and G_2 . It differs from typical constructs used in frameworks akin to ReGs because it features reversion guards. Similarly as for iteration, reversion guards are evaluated locally and, if the guard $\phi_h(B)$ of one of the participants B of G_h ($h \in \{1, 2\}$) evaluates to true, then the execution of the branch h may be reversed to the choice point to attempt the other unexplored branch. To guarantee the progress of a choreography, rolling back a choice construct is forbidden when all but one branch has been tried.

Example 1. The ReG G defined below constitutes the formal counterpart to the workflow in Fig. 2 of the test generation case study of Section 2.

$$\begin{aligned}
 G &= G_0; (\mathbf{branch} \ T\{G_s \text{ unless } \phi_{\text{ratio}} + G_p \text{ unless } \phi_{\text{new}}\}) \quad \text{where:} \\
 G_0 &= R \rightarrow D : \text{code}; D \rightarrow R : \text{pullReq}; R \rightarrow T : \text{startTesting} \\
 G_s &= \mathbf{repeat} \ T\{T \rightarrow M : \text{exhReg}; G'_s\} \\
 G'_s &= \mathbf{repeat} \ L_1\{\mathbf{branch} \ M\{M \rightarrow L_1 : \text{tFail} + M \rightarrow L_1 : \text{tOK}\} \text{ unless } \phi_{\text{diff}}\}; L_1 \rightarrow T : \text{newTest} \\
 G_p &= \mathbf{repeat} \ T\{G'_p\} \mid \mathbf{repeat} \ T\{G''_p\} \\
 G'_p &= T \rightarrow M : \text{chosenTest}; \mathbf{branch} \ M\{M \rightarrow L_g : \text{new} + M \rightarrow L_g : \text{stable}\} \\
 G''_p &= T \rightarrow M : \text{unitTest}; \mathbf{branch} \ M\{M \rightarrow L_1 : \text{tFail} + M \rightarrow L_1 : \text{tOK}\}
 \end{aligned}$$

⁸ Although we only consider *binary* choices, the generalisation to *n*-ary branches is easy.

In particular, G_0 denotes the developer/repository interaction triggering the integration testing, G_s denotes the exhaustive-testing workflow, and G_p denotes the parallel workflow used when a code with new functionalities is submitted. These descriptions incorporate the revision guards ϕ_{ratio} , ϕ_{new} and ϕ_{diff} discussed in Section 2.

4 A monitor-oriented compilation for CI

Our approach advocated in [14] is to keep the *forward behaviour* (i.e. the “normal” execution when nothing has to be reversed) and the *backward behaviour* (i.e. the execution reversal) as separate as possible. This is elegantly rendered in ReGs: developers first specify the forward behaviour as a choreography of *independently executing* participants. Then they describe the alternative behaviour by decorating the choreography with reversion guards. This separation is then reflected in the code that is synthesised from ReGs, where every participant in the workflow is shadowed by a *monitor*. As a result, the participant code contains the forward behaviour (decluttered from the reversibility concerns) whereas the monitor code checks the reversion guard and oversees the respective reverse behaviour.

Participants and their monitors are implemented as Erlang *actors* [18, 1] encapsulating autonomous units of computation. An actor in Erlang [2, 8] runs as a lightweight thread (called a process in Erlang jargon) and has a unique process identifier (PID). Actors interact with each other via asynchronous point-to-point messages, changing their internal state in response to the messages received. Each actor has a *mailbox*, a queue where other actors can send messages in a non-blocking fashion using their PIDs. The messages in a mailbox are then consumed by the recipient actor using pattern matching. This enables the realisation of massively scalable distributed systems.

The single-receiver communication framework of the actor model perfectly matches that of ReGs. An interaction $A \rightarrow B: m$ specifies that the sender A deposits the message m in the queue of the receiver B . These interactions can be directly compiled into snippets of Erlang send and receive operations (in the respective sender and receiver actors). Similarly, the forward behaviour of a distributed choice of a ReG can also be directly compiled in Erlang code. The following snippets illustrate this point using the choice **branch** $M\{M \rightarrow L_1: \text{tFail} + M \rightarrow L_1: \text{tOK}\}$ of G'_s in Section 3:

```

%% code for sender M
case @local decision@ of
true  -> L1 ! {..., tOK};
false -> L1 ! {..., tFail}
end

%% code for receiver L1
receive
{..., tFail} ->
{..., tOK} ->
end

```

The **case** construct in the sender decides which branch to execute by evaluating a boolean expression using only local information; this expression is to be provided by the programmer. The code for L_1 executes a receive command which is guarded by two tuples⁹ that discriminate between the two branches: each of the tuples pattern matches one of the messages sent by M . Once a message matching a tuple is consumed, L_1 will continue with the corresponding branch.

⁹ It suffices to assume that ellipses contain line numbers generated at compile-time to identify interactions, choice points, and iterations. We will be more precise on the tuple format later.

Reverse executions are coordinated by monitors. We start with the reversal of a distributed choice. For each choice the compiler generates the code for coordinating reverse execution. Firstly such code spawns an actor coordinating the choice, say C, which is in charge of deciding whether or not to reverse a choice branch. This decision is taken with the help of a monitor M_C spawned by C. The code for each branch of the choice for the participant A and its monitor M_A is suffixed with a piece of code implementing the following behaviour (cf. Fig. 3 where numbers represent the temporal order):

Fig. 3. Enacting reversibility

- A sends M_A its state of computation to evaluate the guard $\phi(A)$ of A. Then A waits for the decision of C;
- when the decision arrives, A forwards it to M_A and goes back to the choice point if the decision is to rollback, otherwise it finishes the branch;
- M_A sends the result of the evaluation of $\phi(A)$ to M_C , goes back to the choice point when A communicates to reverse, and finishes the choice otherwise;
- the monitor M_C aggregates the evaluations of each guard (after receiving all of them), and sends the result to C;
- C takes the decision and sends it to each participant of the choice.

The last item in the behaviour described above allows C not to reverse a branch depending on certain circumstances. As a result, for example, the last unexplored branch is not reversed no matter how the monitors of participants evaluate their reversion guards.

The behaviour for reversing the iteration construct is very similar to the one for the choice. For each entry point of a loop the compiler generates the code for coordinating the decision to undo execution. Firstly such code spawns an actor, say L, coordinating the loop reversal. This decision is taken by another monitor M_L spawned by L. The code generated for the loop of each participant A and its monitor M_A is suffixed with a piece of code implementing the following behaviour (similar to the behaviour in Fig. 3 but for L replacing C and M_L replacing M_C):

- A sends to M_A the state to evaluate the guard $\phi(A)$ on and waits;
- when the decision from L arrives, A forwards it to M_A and goes back to the entry point of the loop if the decision is to rollback, otherwise it exits the loop;
- M_A sends the result of $\phi(A)$ to M_L , waits for the decision from A and goes back to the loop entry point in case the decision is to reverse, exiting the loop otherwise;
- the monitor M_L aggregates the evaluations of each guard and sends the result to L;
- L takes the decision and sends it to each participant of the iteration.

5 Compiling into Erlang

The main point of our approach is the automatic generation of executable Erlang code from a given ReG. Our compiler produces Erlang code which

- a) generates an actor and the corresponding monitor for each participant of the ReG so to realise forward and reverse computation as specified by the ReG;

Fig. 4. Scheme of compilation for a choice and a loop with respect participant A.

- b) for each choice or iteration in the ReG, it generates the coordinator and its monitor as well as the functions evaluating reversion guards;
- c) realises the behaviours of the different threads of the actors involved in each parallel gate in the ReG (this is not immediate since Erlang actors cannot be multi-threaded).

Next, we outline the main features of the functionalities listed above. For each participant, say A, the compiler creates two functions `ptp_A_fun()` and `mon_ptp_A_fun()` that encapsulate the behaviour of A and its monitor respectively. The compiler generates directly the send or the receive code (depending on whether the participant acts as a sender or as a receiver). The non-trivial aspects of the compilation are the choice, iteration, and parallel composition constructs. We first discuss the choice and iteration constructs, and tackle the parallel composition later.

Fig. 4 sketches the compilation scheme for the participant A involved in a choice or in an iteration. Consider a choice, say **branch** $B\{G_l \text{ unless } \phi_l + G_r \text{ unless } \phi_r\}$, first. The compiler generates a *starting stub* accounting for the monitor of A (i.e., the actor executing `mon_ptp_A_fun()`) and for the coordinator C, and its monitor. The starting stub is represented by the unfilled small square and circle in the leftmost diagram of Fig. 4. This stub spawns the coordinator C of the choice if $A = B$, and then generates an Erlang receive command with two clauses of the form $t_l \rightarrow code_l$ and $t_r \rightarrow code_r$. The tuple t_l (resp. t_r) pattern matches on the messages that C sends to select the branch l (resp. r), after which the code `code_l` (resp. `code_r`) for the behaviour of A in G_l (resp. G_r), represented by $G_l(A)$ (resp. $G_r(A)$), is generated. In both cases the selection message is also propagated to `mon_ptp_A_fun()`. Finally, the compiler generates the *ending stub*. It consists of the code for A that sends its status to its monitor `mon_ptp_A_fun()`, waits for the decision from C, and then propagates the decision to `mon_ptp_A_fun()`. The ending stub is represented in Fig. 4 by the filled small square and circle. The scheme for the iteration construct is similar: the compiler generates the stub deciding whether A has to keep on iterating or to terminate the iteration, and plugs the sub-function corresponding to the behaviour A in the body of the loop (represented by $G_b(A)$), into the stub. This is schematically represented in the rightmost scheme in Fig. 4.

All stubs are then used in the main program generated by the compiler as follows. For each participant A, the compiler adds to the main program the two lines below:

```
register(mon_ptp_A, spawn(..., mon_ptp_A_fun, []))
register(ptp_A, spawn(..., ptp_A_fun, []))
```

The code spawns two actors¹⁰ executing `mon_ptp_A_fun()` and `act_ptp_A_fun()` respectively. The two *registered names* `ptp_A` and `mon_ptp_A` associate atoms¹¹ (i.e. name constants) to PIDs: the generated code then addresses actors using these registered names. Once actors and monitors are spawned, the code contains the lines

```
mon_ptp_A ! go,
ptp_A ! {go, self()},
```

that send a `go` message to the actors to trigger their execution. The expression `self()` returns the PID of the executing actor. This PID is used by `ptp_A` to signal when the behaviour of A has been completely executed (see the first snippet in Section 6).

6 The compiler in action

We now describe how the compilation scheme applies to each construct of a ReGs. In the parsing phase, the compiler assigns a *control point* to each interaction, choice, iteration, and parallel construct. Control points can be thought as the “line number” uniquely identifying the constructs in a ReG¹². Control points allow us to pinpoint at run-time where messages originate from.

Interactions. We explain the compilation of interactions by considering the repository participant R from Example 1. The functions generated for R and its monitor are:

```
ptp_R_fun() ->                               mon_ptp_R_fun() ->
receive {go,Pid} ->                           emptyMonitor
  ptp_D ! {20, code},
  receive {19, pullReq} ->
    %code to be completed%
  end,
  ptp_T ! {18, startTesting},
  Pid ! done_actor
end.
```

After receiving the triggering message from the main actor, the repository R sends the tuple `{20, code}` to the actor `ptp_D` enacting the behaviour of the developer D: this corresponds to the interaction $R \rightarrow D$: `code` in Example 1 (identified with control point 20). Then the actor `ptp_R` collects the pull request (sent from the developer D). Once the tuple `{19, pullReq}` has been consumed, `ptp_R` tells the actor `ptp_T` to start tests and signals its termination to the main. Note that the variable `Pid` is assigned the value of PID of the main when pattern matching the tuple `{go, Pid}`. The actor `mon_ptp_R` does not carry any behaviour since R is not involved in any (reversible) choice or iteration. In fact, monitors are in charge of controlling whether a certain computation has to be reversed, and our ReGs confine reversing of computation to the choice and iteration constructs only.

¹⁰ The ellipses “...” denote the module name, which is one of the inputs to the compiler.

¹¹ In Erlang, atoms start with a lower-case letter, whereas variables start with an upper-case letter.

¹² The ellipsis “...” in the code snippet of Section 4 are control points.

Parallel. Erlang actors cannot be multi-threaded. We need to cope with this limitation, since our workflows may have participants acting in parallel. For instance, the right-hand side branch G_p in Example 1 forks into two parallel flows for M and T.

The compilation of a participant A involved in $n > 1$ threads is attained by spawning n different actors each implementing the behaviour A in one of the threads. The i -th such actor is given the name `ptp_A_CP_i` where CP is the control point assigned to the parallel construct. Other participants that interact with the i -th actor in parallel use this name to communicate with it. For example, the compiler will generate code for registering the actors `ptp_M1_9` and `ptp_M2_9` which represent the behaviours of M in the left- and right-hand side threads. Likewise, for the participant T. As a result, the actor `ptp_M1_9` interacts with the actor `ptp_T1_9` in the left thread of the workflow, while the actors `ptp_M2_9` and `ptp_M2_9` interact in the right thread. Our scheme relaxes the syntactic restrictions of [14] imposing participants to occur at most in one of the threads of a parallel. This allows us to be as expressive as [16, 28].

Consider the following snippet generated by the compiler for the behaviour of M in the right-hand side branch (where 9 is the control point of the parallel construct).

```

1   register(ptp_M1_9, spawn(generation_par,act_ptp_M1_9, [])),      % spawning M1 and M2
2   register(ptp_M2_9, spawn(generation_par,act_ptp_M2_9, [])),      % and registering them
3   lists:foreach(
4     fun(_) -> receive{9,done} -> join end end,
5     [ptp_M1_9,ptp_M2_9])

```

Once the actor spawns its threads (lines 1-2), it waits for their termination. This is rendered as a synchronisation barrier (lines 3-5), where the actor waits for its threads¹³ to send the atom `done`. The compiler has also to “parallelise” the monitor of an actor rendering a thread. For instance, the thread actor `ptp_M1_9` is shadowed by the monitor actor `mon_ptp_M1_9`.

Choice and iteration. We now present two snippets for the choice and iteration constructs according to the scheme in Fig. 3. For each participant A involved in a choice or an iteration with a control point CP, the compiler generates functions `act_ptp_A_CP` and `loop_ptp_A_CP` which realise the behaviour described in the following.

The coordinating actor for the choice is in charge of telling all the actors participating in a distributed choice which branch to take. The coordinator executes the function `sel_act(CP, PtpList)`, where CP is the control point of the choice and PtpList is the list of participants involved in the choice. This function also plays a role in deciding whether a choice or an iteration construct has to be reversed as explained in Section 4. We now focus on the code generated for the outermost choice with respect to the participant T (cf. Fig. 2).

```

1   act_ptp_T17() ->
2     receive
3       {17, left} ->
4         mon_ptp_T ! {17, left},
5         spawn(rgg_support,
6           loop_sel,[16, [ptp_L, ptp_M, ptp_T]]),
7         receive {16, startLoop} -> Loop end,
8         loop_ptp_T16();
9     {17, right} ->
10      mon_ptp_T ! {17, right},
11      %code for parallel OMITTED%
12  end,
13  Info = process_info(self()),
14  mon_ptp_T ! {17, exit, Info},
15  receive
16    {17, fwd} -> mon_ptp_T ! {17, fwd};
17    {17, rev } ->
18      mon_ptp_T ! {17, rev},

```

¹³ The built-in `foreach(F,L)` function of Erlang iterates function F on the elements of list L.

```

19     act_ptp_T_17()
20   end
21 end.
22 mon_ptp_T_17() ->
23   receive
24     {17, left} ->
25     mon_loop_ptp_T_16(),
26     receive{17, exit, Info} -> ok end,
27     Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info);
28     {17, right} ->
29     %code for parallel monitors%
30     receive{17, exit, Info} -> ok end,
31     Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info), mimic)
32   end,
33   Sel = sel_mon_17,
34   case Guard of
35     true -> Sel ! {17, rev};
36     _ -> Sel ! {17, fwd}
37   end,
38   receive
39     {17, rev} -> mon_ptp_T_17();
40     {17, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_T_17
41   end
42 end.

```

The first action of T is to wait for a decision from the coordinating actor whether to take the right branch or the left branch (lines 2-12). Note that the lines 2-4 and 9-12 correspond to the starting stub while the lines 13-21 correspond to the ending stub of the choice construct in Fig. 4. Once this message has been received, the actor notifies its monitor which branch to execute (lines 4 and 10), and then executes the corresponding code (lines 5-6 and 11).

The right-hand side branch of T is a parallel as we have already explained before. The compilation of the loop in the left branch involves the actor coordinating the loop. Similarly to the choice coordinator, this actor decides, at the end of each iteration, whether to continue iterating or to terminate the loop. The function `act_ptp_T_17` spawns the coordinator of the loop (lines 5-6) which executes `loop_sel` with the control point 16 and the list of participants of the loop. Once the message `{16, startLoop}` arrives, the actor for T executes the code for the body of the loop which the compiler wraps in the function `loop_ptp_T_16`.

Once the chosen branch finishes, T sends its status to its monitor (lines 13-14). In our case studies, the status is provided by Erlang's built-in function `process_info(_)` which, given a PID, returns information about the run-time status of the actor identified by the PID [11].

The monitor evaluates the guard after receiving the status from T in both branches (lines 26-27 and 30-31). The monitor sends either `{17, rev}` or `{17, fwd}` to the coordinator's monitor (depending on the value of the guard), and then waits for the decision of the coordinator to be propagated (lines 38-40). The monitor of the coordinator collects all the decisions from the monitors of the actors participating in the choice, aggregates them and sends the outcome to the coordinator. The aggregation is the tuple `{17, rev}` if at least one of the decisions is to revert, otherwise it is `{17, fwd}`. When T receives the decision of the coordinator (lines 15-20), it propagates the decision to its monitor and acts according to the decision, namely it either reverses the branch or continues with the forward execution.

Iterations are rendered in a similar way using the guards to decide whether or not to repeat an iteration.

Guards. As we have explained in Section 3, ϕ is a map that assigns a condition to each participant. The compiler renders conditions as boolean functions. Consider the participant M in the example of Fig. 2. The conditions of M are locally evaluated functions that take status information as input and return a boolean. The reversion guards ϕ_{new} and ϕ_{ratio} for M give rise to the following two functions:

```

new_bug(Info) ->
{_, Status} = Info,
L = lists:filter(
  fun(X) ->
    case X of
      {bug,_} -> true;
      _ -> false
    end
  end,
  Status),
case L of
[] -> true ;
_ -> false
end.

check_ratio(Info) ->
threshold = %some constant%
{_, Status} = Info,
{_,New} = lists:filter(
  fun(X) ->
    case X of {newbug,_} -> true ; _ -> false end
  end,
  Status),
{_,Old} = lists:filter(
  fun(X) ->
    case X of {oldbug,_} -> true ; _ -> false end
  end,
  Status),
New / New + Old > Threshold.

```

The first function says that right-hand side branch needs to be reversed when a test has started failing (possibly a new bug). The second function requires a reversal of the left-hand side branch if the ratio of new failures to the old failures is above a certain threshold. The reversion guards ϕ_{new} and ϕ_{ratio} for all the remaining participants in the choice are constantly `false`, meaning they never ask for a reversal of the branch.

7 Conclusions

Summary We proposed reversibility-enabling graphs (ReGs) as a high level formalism for describing distributed CI behaviours. This necessitated that we enhanced the expressivity of ReGs by extending reversibility capabilities to loops, and weaken restrictions such as the one limiting participants to a single-thread in a parallel compositions [14, 28]. We also evidenced the usefulness and the benefits of our approach in two case studies on automated test generation (ATG) and a flakiness detection (FD). We also demonstrated how to compile ReGs in executable Erlang code. Our framework naturally provides support for FD and ATG in terms of controlled reversibility. This is attained while hiding away from the user the scaffolding for reversibility: the declarative flavour of our abstractions simply requires the user to declare reversion guards. Then all the coordination among participants is automatically derived.

Discussion of Advantages We revisit some of related work discussed in Sections 1 to 3 and compare it with ours. The main benefits of our approach are:

- a) a declarative mechanism for controlled reversibility (through reversion guards) as an abstraction for automated test generation and flakiness detection in CI;
- b) the automatic generation of executable pipelines that allows lifts the burden of implementing complex coordination among components involved in CI and facilitates pipelines' evolution and maintainability; and
- c) the correct-by-construction realisation of CI pipelines achieved by means of a model-driven framework based on choreographies.

The support for FD and ATG could be directly programmed in one of the scripting languages for CI. For instance, Jenkin's *checkpoints* are similar to exceptions and have been introduced to cope with failure recovery¹⁴. Let us demonstrate how such mechanisms could be used to program the reversal of computation.

Take the choice construct and assume to have the following two functions (in a fictional syntax):

¹⁴ We note that reversion guards are general and high-level enough to deal with failure recovery.

```
fun branch_then() { ... throw ... }
fun branch_else() { ... throw ... }
```

where the **throw** will rise an exception when the condition of the branch is not satisfied. If one branch fails we could use the following code to explore the other branch:

```
if //condition to take one branch
try { branch_then() } catch() { branch_else() }
else try { branch_else() } catch() { branch_then() }
```

This programming pattern has to be applied to all the (possibly nested) choices of the branches, resulting in an error prone and non modular code. Moreover, in distributed CI the pattern above becomes even more complex; in fact,

- each participant, say A, in a choice has to notify the others once an exception to catch a branch is caught (this means that the code of the participant has to be somehow pre-empted with respect to messages from the other participants in the choice.) and, more crucially,
- these notifications must be used to solve a distributed consensus problem, which involves the decision whether to reverse the computation or not.

Similar concerns apply also to iterations.

The code that the user has to provide for the reversion guards in our case studies is very small: see the lines 291-299 in Appendix A.1 and the lines 1101-1130 in Appendix A.2. In contrast, the total size of the code generated for our case studies consist of ~400 and ~1200 lines of code. On the one hand, these experiments are indicative of the complexity involved in implementing reversible mechanisms. On the other hand, they highlight how working with good abstraction help with aspects such as code readability and maintainability. As with any software artefacts, CI pipeline may evolve over time. For instance, new heuristics may have to be used which change the entire behaviour of a pipeline. In this case, our approach simply requires the user to change some of reversion guards without modifying the forward behaviour of the pipeline. Also, a change in the branching structure of a pipeline would require to modify the ReG model and automatically generate new code. By contrast, using a manual approach would require the user to write new code (when branches are added) and modify existing code since the code to support FD or ATG is entangled with exception handling mechanisms.

Besides the advantages provided by the use of controlled reversibility for CI, ReGs yield other benefits, such as the *correct-by-design* principle (beneficial to the development of distributed workflows in general). The compilation scheme of Section 4 guarantees communication soundness *by-construction* using the well known results on behavioural types [20, 28, 19]. More precisely, it is known that when, for each choice or iteration,

- there is a unique selector of branches or loop termination/continuation,
- the messages used to communicate the selector’s decision are, “unambiguous”
- all participants are informed of the selector’s decisions,

then the communication logic of the workflow is sound. Our compilation scheme fulfils all the above conditions, hence the designers do not have to worry about the correctness of the communication pattern of their workflow. This means that pipelines obtained compiling ReGs cannot deadlock or have loss of messages.

Future work The motivation for using Erlang is that its programs can be easily distributed and scaled up well due to the underlying actor model. As a future work we plan to integrate the Erlang generated code with CI scripts. This would enable us to empower our generated code with the features of these domain-specific languages. The correct-by-construction benefit comes at a price: there is an overhead of communications that could sometimes be reduced using some known results of behavioural types. The compiler could be extended with a static analysis of the workflow to identify when the control point-based messages sent by the coordinators are necessary. We illustrate this by considering the workflow for test generation (cf. Section 2). The participant M does not need to interact with the coordinator of the choice because the different messages it receives from T already identify the chosen branch. Also, there is no need to create the thread actors for L_g and L_l when the parallel pipeline is chosen. In fact, both these participants are involved only in one of the threads. An improvement of our compiler in this direction is possible by implementing optimisations such as those in [28].

References

1. G. Agha. *Actors: A Model of Concurrent Computation in Distributed Systems*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, USA, 1986.
2. J. Armstrong. *Programming Erlang: Software for a Concurrent World*. Pragmatic Bookshelf, 2007.
3. F. Barbanera, I. Lanese, and U. de'Liguoro. A theory of retractable and speculative contracts. *Science of Computer Programming*, 167:25–50, 2018.
4. J. Bell, O. Legunsen, M. Hilton, L. Eloussi, T. Yung, and D. Marinov. DeFlaker: Automatically detecting flaky tests. In *Intl. Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, pages 433–444. ACM, 2018.
5. J. Campos, A. Arcuri, G. Fraser, and R. Abreu. Continuous test generation: Enhancing continuous integration with automated test generation. In *ACM/IEEE Intl. Conference on Automated Software Engineering (ASE)*, pages 55–66. ACM, 2014.
6. I. Cassar and A. Francalanza. On Implementing a Monitor-Oriented Programming Framework for Actor Systems. In *iFM, LNCS*, pages 176–192. Springer, 2016.
7. I. Castellani, M. Dezani-Ciancaglini, and P. Giannini. Concurrent reversible sessions. In R. Meyer and U. Nestmann, editors, *28th International Conference on Concurrency Theory, CONCUR 2017*, volume 85 of *LIPICs*, pages 30:1–30:17. Schloss Dagstuhl - Leibniz-Zentrum fuer Informatik, 2017.
8. F. Cesarini and S. Thompson. *Erlang Programming*. O'Reilly, 2009.
9. R. Chuck. Rapid release at massive scale. <https://code.fb.com/web/rapid-release-at-massive-scale/>, 2017.
10. P. Deniérou and N. Yoshida. Multiparty session types meet communicating automata. In H. Seidl, editor, *Programming Languages and Systems - 21st European Symposium on Programming, ESOP 2012*, volume 7211 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 194–213. Springer, 2012.
11. Erlang Run-Time System Application, Reference Manual Version 9.2. Available at <http://erlang.org/doc/man/erlang.html>.
12. B. Fitzgerald and K.-J. Stol. Continuous software engineering: A roadmap and agenda. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 123:176 – 189, 2017.
13. M. Fowler. Continuous Integration. <https://martinfowler.com/articles/continuousIntegration.html>, 2006.

14. A. Francalanza, C. A. Mezzina, and E. Tuosto. Reversible choreographies via monitoring in erlang. In S. Bonomi and E. Rivière, editors, *Distributed Applications and Interoperable Systems - 18th IFIP WG 6.1 International Conference, DAIS 2018*, volume 10853 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 75–92. Springer, 2018.
15. M. Grosser. Big and Fast Tests: Taking our Travis build from 4 hours to 13 minutes. <https://developer.zendesk.com/blog/big-and-fast-tests-taking-our-travis-build-from-4-hours-to-13-minutes>, 2015.
16. R. Guanciale and E. Tuosto. An abstract semantics of the global view of choreographies. In *ICE*, volume 223 of *EPTCS*, pages 67–82, 2016.
17. P. Gupta, M. Ivey, and J. Penix. Testing at the speed and scale of google. <http://google-engtools.blogspot.com/2011/06/testing-at-speed-and-scale-of-google.html>, 2011. Posted by jthomas.
18. C. Hewitt, P. Bishop, and R. Steiger. A Universal Modular ACTOR Formalism for Artificial Intelligence. In *International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence IJCAI*. Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., 1973.
19. K. Honda, N. Yoshida, and M. Carbone. Multiparty asynchronous session types. *Journal of ACM*, 63(1):9:1–9:67, 2016.
20. H. Hüttel, I. Lanese, V. T. Vasconcelos, L. Caires, M. Carbone, P. Deniérou, D. Mostrous, L. Padovani, A. Ravara, E. Tuosto, H. T. Vieira, and G. Zavattaro. Foundations of session types and behavioural contracts. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 49(1):3:1–3:36, 2016.
21. I. Lanese, C. A. Mezzina, A. Schmitt, and J. Stefani. Controlling reversibility in higher-order pi. In J. Katoen and B. König, editors, *CONCUR 2011 - Concurrency Theory - 22nd International Conference*, volume 6901 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 297–311. Springer, 2011.
22. I. Lanese, C. A. Mezzina, and J. Stefani. Reversibility in the higher-order π -calculus. *Theoretical Computer Science*, 625:25–84, 2016.
23. Q. Luo, F. Hariri, L. Eloussi, and D. Marinov. An empirical analysis of flaky tests. In *ACM SIGSOFT Intl. Symposium on Foundations of Software Engineering (FSE)*, pages 643–653. ACM, 2014.
24. M. Naele. Parallelism and Distributed Builds in Jenkins. <https://www.cloudbees.com/blog/parallelism-and-distributed-builds-jenkins>, 2015.
25. I. Phillips, I. Ulidowski, and S. Yuen. A reversible process calculus and the modelling of the ERK signalling pathway. In R. Glück and T. Yokoyama, editors, *Reversible Computation 2012*, volume 7581 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 218–232. Springer, 2012.
26. I. C. C. Phillips and I. Ulidowski. Reversing algebraic process calculi. *Journal of Logic and Algebraic Programming*, 73(1-2):70–96, 2007.
27. D. Ståhl and J. Bosch. Modeling continuous integration practice differences in industry software development. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 87:48 – 59, 2014.
28. E. Tuosto and R. Guanciale. Semantics of global view of choreographies. *Journal of Logic and Algebraic Methods in Programming*, 95:17–40, 2018.
29. B. Vasilescu, Y. Yu, H. Wang, P. Devanbu, and V. Filkov. Quality and productivity outcomes relating to continuous integration in github. In *10th Joint Meeting on Foundations of Software Engineering, ESEC/FSE 2015*, pages 805–816. ACM, 2015.
30. S. Yoo and M. Harman. Regression testing minimization, selection and prioritization: A survey. *Software: Testing, Verification and Reliability*, 22(2):67–120, Mar. 2012.

A Synthesised Code

In this Section we report the code of the two cases study which have been generated starting from their respective ReGs. Plus we report the code for `rgg_support`, which is a module containing additional functions for the right functioning of the code. Let us note that this last file is not automatically generated.

To execute both the examples, copy the three listings above in three different files named as their module names then:

- open the Erlang shell in the same directory where the code is;
- type the command “`cover:compile_directory().`”;
- type either “`code_gen:main().`” or “`flaky:main().`” to run the example.

A.1 Flakyness Detection

Code for the flakyness detection case study. Note that in order to use it you need also to compile the file.

```

1 -module(flaky).

2 %% -----
3 %% Import helper functions

4 -export([act_ptp_C_7/0,
5         mon_ptp_C_7/0,
6         act_ptp_L_7/0,
7         mon_ptp_L_7/0,
8         act_ptp_M_7/0,
9         mon_ptp_M_7/0,
10        act_ptp_T_7/0,
11        mon_ptp_T_7/0,
12        loop_ptp_M_2/0,
13        loop_ptp_C_2/0,
14        loop_ptp_M_5/0,
15        loop_ptp_L_5/0,
16        mon_loop_ptp_L_5/0,
17        mon_loop_ptp_M_5/0,
18        mon_loop_ptp_C_2/0,
19        mon_loop_ptp_M_2/0,
20        ptp_C_fun/0, mon_ptp_C_fun/0,
21        ptp_L_fun/0, mon_ptp_L_fun/0,
22        ptp_M_fun/0, mon_ptp_M_fun/0,
23        ptp_T_fun/0, mon_ptp_T_fun/0,
24        main/0]).

25 %% -----
26 %% The code to chose a branch...trivial for the moment

27 -import(rgg_support,
28        [smartReg/3,
29         notify/3,
30         loop_sel/6,
31         sel_act/4,
32         sel_mon/3,
33         debug/4,
34         getBranch/1,
35         debugLoop/0
36 ]).

```

```

37 %% -----
38 procInfo() -> process_info_self
39 .
40 %% -----
41 checkGuard(Phi, Info) -> checkGuard(Phi, Info, revOnly).

42 %% -----
43 %% Eventually only checkGuard/3 should be used

44 checkGuard(Phi, Info, Mode) ->
45   case Mode of
46     random -> % random check for test only
47       case rand:uniform(2) of
48         1 -> true;
49         2 -> false
50       end;
51     fwdOnly -> false; % this should behave according to the standard
52     ↪ semantics
53     revOnly -> true; % this reverses as much as possible all the branches
54     mimic -> true; % this takes the dual branch taken in the standard
55     ↪ semantics and reverses them
56     std -> false;
57     guard -> Phi(Info)
58   end.

59 %% -----
60 %% Actor for participant ptp_M of c.p. 5

61 loop_ptp_M_5() ->
62   debug("[p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [4, ptp_M, ptp_L, [testRes]], 1, 13),
63   ptp_L ! {4, testRes},
64   debug("[p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [5, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
65   mon_ptp_M ! {5, itrDone, infos},
66   receive
67     {5, loopBack} -> debug("[p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [5, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [loopBack]], 1, 13),
68     mon_ptp_M ! {5, loopBack},
69     loop_ptp_M_5();
70     {5, rollBack} -> debug("[p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [5, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [rollBack]], 1, 13),
71     mon_ptp_M ! {5, rollBack},
72     loop_ptp_M_5();
73     {5, exitLoop} -> debug("[p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [5, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [exitLoop]], 1, 13),
74     mon_ptp_M ! {5, exitLoop}
75   end
76 .

77 %% -----
78 %% Monitor for participant ptp_M of c.p. 5

79 mon_loop_ptp_M_5() ->
80   receive
81     {5, itrDone, Info} ->
82     case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
83       true -> debug("[p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [5, mon_ptp_M_5, sel_mon_5, [rev]], 1, 13),
84       sel_mon_5 ! {5, rev};
85       _ -> debug("[p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [5, mon_ptp_M_5, sel_mon_5, [fwd]], 1, 13),
86       sel_mon_5 ! {5, fwd}
87     end,
88   receive

```

20 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

87         {5, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
88         {5, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_M_5();
89         {5, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_M_5()

90     end
91 end.

92 %% -----
93 %% Actor for participant ptp_L of c.p. 5

94 loop_ptp_L_5() ->
95     receive {4, testRes} -> debug("[^p]   ^p ? ^p : ^p", [4, ptp_M, ptp_L, [testRes]], 1,
96         ↪ 13)end,
97     debug("[^p]   ^p ! ^p : ^p", [5, ptp_L, mon_ptp_L, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
98 mon_ptp_L ! {5, itrDone, infos},
99     receive
100     {5, loopBack} -> debug("[^p]   ^p ! ^p : ^p", [5, ptp_L, mon_ptp_L, [loopBack]], 1, 13),
101 mon_ptp_L ! {5, loopBack},
102 loop_ptp_L_5();
103     {5, rollBack} -> debug("[^p]   ^p ! ^p : ^p", [5, ptp_L, mon_ptp_L, [rollBack]], 1, 13),
104 mon_ptp_L ! {5, rollBack},
105 loop_ptp_L_5();
106     {5, exitLoop} -> debug("[^p]   ^p ! ^p : ^p", [5, ptp_L, mon_ptp_L, [exitLoop]], 1, 13),
107 mon_ptp_L ! {5, exitLoop}
108     end
109 .

110 %% -----
111 %% Monitor for participant ptp_L of c.p. 5

112 mon_loop_ptp_L_5() ->
113     receive
114         {5, itrDone, Info} ->
115         case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
116         true -> debug("[^p]   ^p ! ^p : ^p", [5, mon_ptp_L_5, sel_mon_5, [rev]], 1, 13),
117 sel_mon_5 ! {5, rev};
118         _ -> debug("[^p]   ^p ! ^p : ^p", [5, mon_ptp_L_5, sel_mon_5, [fwd]], 1, 13),
119 sel_mon_5 ! {5, fwd}
120     end,
121     receive
122     {5, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
123     {5, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_L_5();
124     {5, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_L_5()

125 end
126 end.

127 %% -----
128 %% Actor for participant ptp_M of c.p. 2

129 loop_ptp_M_2() ->
130     debug("[^p]   ^p ! ^p : ^p", [1, ptp_M, ptp_C, [testRes]], 1, 13),
131 ptp_C ! {1, testRes},
132     debug("[^p]   ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
133 mon_ptp_M ! {2, itrDone, infos},
134     receive
135     {2, loopBack} -> debug("[^p]   ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [loopBack]], 1, 13),
136 mon_ptp_M ! {2, loopBack},
137 loop_ptp_M_2();
138     {2, rollBack} -> debug("[^p]   ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [rollBack]], 1, 13),
139 mon_ptp_M ! {2, rollBack},
140 loop_ptp_M_2();
141     {2, exitLoop} -> debug("[^p]   ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [exitLoop]], 1, 13),
142 mon_ptp_M ! {2, exitLoop}
143     end
144 .

```

```

144 %% -----
145 %% Monitor for participant ptp_M of c.p. 2

146 mon_loop_ptp_M_2() ->
147   receive
148     {2, itrDone, Info} ->
149     case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
150       true -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [2, mon_ptp_M_2, sel_mon_2, [rev]], 1, 13),
151     sel_mon_2 ! {2, rev};
152     _ -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [2, mon_ptp_M_2, sel_mon_2, [fwd]], 1, 13),
153     sel_mon_2 ! {2, fwd}
154   end,
155   receive
156     {2, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
157     {2, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_M_2();
158     {2, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_M_2()

159   end
160 end.

161 %% -----
162 %% Actor for participant ptp_C of c.p. 2

163 loop_ptp_C_2() ->
164   receive {1, testRes} -> debug("[p]   ~p ? ~p : ~p", [1, ptp_M, ptp_C, [testRes]], 1,
165     ↪ 13)end,
166   debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [2, ptp_C, mon_ptp_C, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
167   mon_ptp_C ! {2, itrDone, infos},
168   receive
169     {2, loopBack} -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [2, ptp_C, mon_ptp_C, [loopBack]], 1, 13),
170     mon_ptp_C ! {2, loopBack},
171     loop_ptp_C_2();
172     {2, rollBack} -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [2, ptp_C, mon_ptp_C, [rollBack]], 1, 13),
173     mon_ptp_C ! {2, rollBack},
174     loop_ptp_C_2();
175     {2, exitLoop} -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [2, ptp_C, mon_ptp_C, [exitLoop]], 1, 13),
176     mon_ptp_C ! {2, exitLoop}
177   end
178 .

178 %% -----
179 %% Monitor for participant ptp_C of c.p. 2

180 mon_loop_ptp_C_2() ->
181   receive
182     {2, itrDone, Info} ->
183     case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
184       true -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [2, mon_ptp_C_2, sel_mon_2, [rev]], 1, 13),
185     sel_mon_2 ! {2, rev};
186     _ -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [2, mon_ptp_C_2, sel_mon_2, [fwd]], 1, 13),
187     sel_mon_2 ! {2, fwd}
188   end,
189   receive
190     {2, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
191     {2, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_C_2();
192     {2, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_C_2()

193   end
194 end.

195 %% -----
196 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_C of the choice at 7

```

22 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

197 act_ptp_C_7() ->
198     receive
199         {7, left} ->
200             debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_C, mon_ptp_C, [left]], 1, 13),
201 mon_ptp_C ! {7, left};
202         {7, right} ->
203             debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_C, mon_ptp_C, [right]], 1, 13),
204 mon_ptp_C ! {7, right},
205 receive {2, startLoop} -> debug("^p starts loop ^p", [ptp_C, 2], debugLoop(), 13) end,
206 loop_ptp_C_2()
207     end,
208     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_C, mon_ptp_C, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
209 mon_ptp_C ! {7, exit, infos},
210 receive
211     {7, fwd} ->
212         debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_C, mon_ptp_C, [fwd]], 1, 13),
213 mon_ptp_C ! {7, fwd};
214     {7, rev } ->
215         debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_C, mon_ptp_C, [rev]], 1, 13),
216 mon_ptp_C ! {7, rev},
217     act_ptp_C_7()
218 end.

219 mon_ptp_C_7() ->
220     receive
221         {7, left} ->
222             receive{7, exit, Info} -> ok end,
223             Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
224         ;
225         {7, right} ->
226             mon_loop_ptp_C_2()
227         ,
228             receive{7, exit, Info} -> ok end,
229             Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
230     end,
231 Sel = sel_mon_7,
232     case Guard of
233     true -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, mon_ptp_C_7, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
234 Sel ! {7, rev};
235     _ -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, mon_ptp_C_7, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
236 Sel ! {7, fwd}
237 end,
238     receive
239     {7, rev} -> mon_ptp_C_7();
240     {7, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_C_7
241 end.

242 %% -----
243 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_C of the choice at 7 done

244 %% -----
245 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_L of the choice at 7

246 act_ptp_L_7() ->
247     receive
248         {7, left} ->
249             debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_L, mon_ptp_L, [left]], 1, 13),
250 mon_ptp_L ! {7, left},
251 receive {5, startLoop} -> debug("^p starts loop ^p", [ptp_L, 5], debugLoop(), 13) end,
252 loop_ptp_L_5();
253         {7, right} ->
254             debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_L, mon_ptp_L, [right]], 1, 13),
255 mon_ptp_L ! {7, right}
256     end,

```

```

257     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [7, ptp_L, mon_ptp_L, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
258 mon_ptp_L ! {7, exit, infos},
259 receive
260     {7, fwd} ->
261     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [7, ptp_L, mon_ptp_L, [fwd]], 1, 13),
262 mon_ptp_L ! {7, fwd};
263     {7, rev } ->
264     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [7, ptp_L, mon_ptp_L, [rev]], 1, 13),
265 mon_ptp_L ! {7, rev},
266     act_ptp_L_7()
267 end.

268 mon_ptp_L_7() ->
269 receive
270     {7, left} ->
271     mon_loop_ptp_L_5(),
272     receive{7, exit, Info} -> ok end,
273     Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly);
274     {7, right} ->
275     receive{7, exit, Info} -> ok end,
276     Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
277 end,
278 Sel = sel_mon_7,
279     case Guard of
280     true -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [7, mon_ptp_L_7, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
281     Sel ! {7, rev};
282     _ -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [7, mon_ptp_L_7, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
283     Sel ! {7, fwd}
284 end,
285 receive
286     {7, rev} -> mon_ptp_L_7();
287     {7, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_L_7
288 end.

289 %% -----
290 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_L of the choice at 7 done

291 %reversion guards for M%
292 check_flipping(Info) ->
293     {_, Status} = Info,
294     L = lists:filter(fun(X) -> case X of {flipping,_} -> true ; _ -> false end end, Status),
295     case L of
296     [{_,true}] -> io:format("flipping!!!\n"),true ;
297     _ -> io:format("no flipping!!!\n"), false
298     end
299 .

300 %% -----
301 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_M of the choice at 7

302 act_ptp_M_7() ->
303 receive
304     {7, left} ->
305     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [7, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [left]], 1, 13),
306     mon_ptp_M ! {7, left},
307     receive {6, testOD} ->debug("[p]   p ? p : p", [6, ptp_T, ptp_M, [testOD]],
308     ↪ 1, 13)end,
309     debug("[p]   Selector started", [5], 1, 13),
310     spawn(rgg_support,loop_sel,[5, [ptp_L, ptp_M], 3, 0, fwdOnly, entireIteration]),
311     receive {5, startLoop} -> debug("p starts loop p", [ptp_M, 5], debugLoop(), 13)
312     ↪ end,
313     loop_ptp_M_5(),
314     %instrumented code
315     case rand:uniform(3) of
316     3 -> put (flipping,true);

```

24 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

315         _ -> put(flipping,false)
316     end;
317     {7, right} ->
318     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [right]], 1, 13),
319     mon_ptp_M ! {7, right},
320     receive {3, testC} -> debug("[^p] ^p ? ^p : ^p", [3, ptp_T, ptp_M, [testC]], 1,
321     ↪ 13)end,
322     debug("[^p] Selector started", [2], 1, 13),
323     spawn(rgg_support,loop_sel,[2, [ptp_C, ptp_M], 3, 0, fwdOnly, entireIteration]),
324     receive {2, startLoop} -> debug("^p starts loop ^p", [ptp_M, 2], debugLoop(), 13)
325     ↪ end,
326     loop_ptp_M_2()
327 end,
328 debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
329 mon_ptp_M ! {7, exit,process_info(self(),dictionary)},
330 receive
331 {7, fwd} ->
332 debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [fwd]], 1, 13),
333 mon_ptp_M ! {7, fwd};
334 {7, rev } ->
335 debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [rev]], 1, 13),
336 mon_ptp_M ! {7, rev},
337 act_ptp_M_7()
338 end.

339 mon_ptp_M_7() ->
340 receive
341 {7, left} ->
342     mon_loop_ptp_M_5(),
343     receive{7, exit, Info} -> ok end,
344     Guard = check_flipping(Info)
345 ;
346 {7, right} ->
347     mon_loop_ptp_M_2(),
348     receive{7, exit, Info} -> ok end,
349     Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
350 end,
351 Sel = sel_mon_7,
352 case Guard of
353 true -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, mon_ptp_M_7, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
354 Sel ! {7, rev};
355 _ -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, mon_ptp_M_7, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
356 Sel ! {7, fwd}
357 end,
358 receive
359 {7, rev} -> mon_ptp_M_7();
360 {7, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_M_7
361 end.

362 %% -----
363 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_M of the choice at 7 done

364 %% -----
365 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_T of the choice at 7

366 act_ptp_T_7() ->
367 receive
368 {7, left} ->
369     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [left]], 1, 13),
370     mon_ptp_T ! {7, left},
371     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [6, ptp_T, ptp_M, [testOD]], 1, 13),
372     ptp_M ! {6, testOD};
373 {7, right} ->
374     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [right]], 1, 13),

```

```

373 mon_ptp_T ! {7, right},
374 debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [3, ptp_T, ptp_M, [testC]], 1, 13),
375 ptp_M ! {3, testC}
376     end,
377     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
378 mon_ptp_T ! {7, exit, infos},
379 receive
380     {7, fwd} ->
381         debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [fwd]], 1, 13),
382 mon_ptp_T ! {7, fwd};
383     {7, rev } ->
384         debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [rev]], 1, 13),
385 mon_ptp_T ! {7, rev},
386         act_ptp_T_7()
387 end.

388 mon_ptp_T_7() ->
389     receive
390         {7, left} ->
391             receive{7, exit, Info} -> ok end,
392             Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
393         ;
394         {7, right} ->
395             receive{7, exit, Info} -> ok end,
396             Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
397     end,
398 Sel = sel_mon_7,
399     case Guard of
400     true -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, mon_ptp_T_7, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
401 Sel ! {7, rev};
402     _ -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [7, mon_ptp_T_7, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
403 Sel ! {7, fwd}
404 end,
405     receive
406     {7, rev} -> mon_ptp_T_7();
407     {7, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_T_7
408 end.

409 %% -----
410 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_T of the choice at 7 done

411 mon_ptp_C_fun() -> receive go -> going end,
412 mon_ptp_C_7()
413 .

414 ptp_C_fun() -> receive {go,Pid} ->act_ptp_C_7()
415 , Pid ! done_actor end
416 .

417 mon_ptp_L_fun() -> receive go -> going end,
418 mon_ptp_L_7()
419 .

420 ptp_L_fun() -> receive {go,Pid} ->act_ptp_L_7()
421 , Pid ! done_actor end
422 .

423 mon_ptp_M_fun() -> receive go -> going end,
424 mon_ptp_M_7()
425 .

426 ptp_M_fun() -> receive {go,Pid} ->act_ptp_M_7()
427 , Pid ! done_actor end
428 .

429 mon_ptp_T_fun() -> receive go -> going end,
430 mon_ptp_T_7()
431 .

```

26 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```
432 ptp_T_fun() -> receive {go,Pid} ->smartReg(sel_7, spawn(rgg_support, sel_act, [], 7, [ptp_C,  
→ ptp_L, ptp_M, ptp_T], fun () -> getBranch([7, fwdOnly, branching_table] end)), 13),  
433 act_ptp_T7()  
434 , Pid ! done_actor end  
435 .  
436 main() ->  
437     case lists:member(branching_table, ets:all()) of  
438     true -> ets:delete(branching_table);  
439     _ -> noTable  
440     end,  
441     ets:new(branching_table, [set, named_table, public]),  
442     ets:insert(branching_table, {7, 1}),  
443     ets:insert(branching_table, {5, 3}),  
444     ets:insert(branching_table, {2, 3}),  
445     ets:insert(branching_table,{debug,13}),  
446     smartReg(mon_ptp_C, spawn(flaky, mon_ptp_C_fun, []), 13),  
447     smartReg(ptp_C, spawn(flaky, ptp_C_fun, []), 13),  
448     smartReg(mon_ptp_L, spawn(flaky, mon_ptp_L_fun, []), 13),  
449     smartReg(ptp_L, spawn(flaky, ptp_L_fun, []), 13),  
450     smartReg(mon_ptp_M, spawn(flaky, mon_ptp_M_fun, []), 13),  
451     smartReg(ptp_M, spawn(flaky, ptp_M_fun, []), 13),  
452     smartReg(mon_ptp_T, spawn(flaky, mon_ptp_T_fun, []), 13),  
453     smartReg(ptp_T, spawn(flaky, ptp_T_fun, []), 13),  
454     STime = os:system_time(),ptp_C ! {go, self()},  
455     mon_ptp_C ! go,  
456     ptp_L ! {go, self()},  
457     mon_ptp_L ! go,  
458     ptp_M ! {go, self()},  
459     mon_ptp_M ! go,  
460     ptp_T ! {go, self()},  
461     mon_ptp_T ! go,  
462     receive done_actor -> ok end,  
463     receive done_actor -> ok end,  
464     receive done_actor -> ok end,  
465     receive done_actor -> ok end,  
466     file:write_file(".time.tmp", integer_to_list(os:system_time() - STime))  
467     .
```

A.2 Code Generation

Code for the test generation case study. Note that in order to use it you need also to compile the file.

```

1 -module(code_gen).

2 %% -----
3 %% Import helper functions

4 -export([act_ptp_Lg_17/0,
5         mon_ptp_Lg_17/0,
6         act_ptp_Ll_17/0,
7         mon_ptp_Ll_17/0,
8         act_ptp_M_17/0,
9         mon_ptp_M_17/0,
10        act_ptp_T_17/0,
11        mon_ptp_T_17/0,
12        loop_ptp_T_8/0,
13        loop_ptp_M_8/0,
14        loop_ptp_Lg_8/0,
15        act_ptp_Lg_6/0,
16        mon_ptp_Lg_6/0,
17        act_ptp_M_6/0,
18        mon_ptp_M_6/0,
19        loop_ptp_T_2/0,
20        loop_ptp_M_2/0,
21        loop_ptp_Ll_2/0,
22        act_ptp_Ll_22/0,
23        mon_ptp_Ll_22/0,
24        act_ptp_M_22/0,
25        mon_ptp_M_22/0,
26        loop_ptp_T_16/0,
27        loop_ptp_M_16/0,
28        loop_ptp_Ll_16/0,
29        loop_ptp_M_14/0,
30        loop_ptp_Ll_14/0,
31        act_ptp_Ll_13/0,
32        mon_ptp_Ll_13/0,
33        act_ptp_M_13/0,
34        mon_ptp_M_13/0,
35        mon_loop_ptp_Ll_14/0,
36        mon_loop_ptp_M_14/0,
37        mon_loop_ptp_Ll_16/0,
38        mon_loop_ptp_M_16/0,
39        mon_loop_ptp_T_16/0,
40        mon_loop_ptp_Ll_2/0,
41        mon_loop_ptp_M_2/0,
42        mon_loop_ptp_T_2/0,
43        mon_loop_ptp_Lg_8/0,
44        mon_loop_ptp_M_8/0,
45        mon_loop_ptp_T_8/0,

46        %actor threads%
47        act_ptp_M2_9/0,
48        act_ptp_M1_9/0,
49        act_ptp_T2_9/0,
50        act_ptp_T1_9/0,

51        %monitor threads
52        mon_ptp_M2_9/0,
53        mon_ptp_M1_9/0,
54        mon_ptp_T2_9/0,
55        mon_ptp_T1_9/0,

```

```

56     %guards
57     %new_bug/0,
58     %check_ratio/0,

59     ptp_D_fun/0, mon_ptp_D_fun/0,
60     ptp_Lg_fun/0, mon_ptp_Lg_fun/0,
61     ptp_Ll_fun/0, mon_ptp_Ll_fun/0,
62     ptp_M_fun/0, mon_ptp_M_fun/0,
63     ptp_R_fun/0, mon_ptp_R_fun/0,
64     ptp_T_fun/0, mon_ptp_T_fun/0,
65     main/0}).

66 %% -----
67 %% The code to chose a branch...trivial for the moment

68 -import (rgg_support,
69         [smartReg/3,
70         smartUnreg/1,
71         while/3,
72         notify/3,
73         loop_sel/6,
74         sel_act/4,
75         sel_mon/3,
76         debug/4,
77         getBranch/1,
78         debugLoop/0,
79         lookup/2]).

80 %% -----

81 procInfo() -> process_info_self
82 .

83 %% -----

84 checkGuard(Phi, Info) -> checkGuard(Phi, Info, revOnly).

85 %% -----
86 %% Eventually only checkGuard/3 should be used

87 checkGuard(Phi, Info, Mode) ->
88     case Mode of
89     random -> % random check for test only
90         case rand:uniform(2) of
91             1 -> true;
92             2 -> false
93         end;
94     fwdOnly -> false; % this should behave according to the standard
95     ⇐ semantics
96     revOnly -> true; % this reverses as much as possible all the branches
97     mimic -> true; % this takes the dual branch taken in the standard
98     ⇐ semantics and reverses them
99     std -> false;
100    guard -> Phi(Info)
101 end.

100 %% -----
101 %% Actor for participant ptp_T of c.p. 16

102 loop_ptp_T_16() ->
103     debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [15, ptp_T, ptp_M, [exhReg]], 1, 13),
104     ptp_M ! {15, exhReg},
105     debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [16, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),

```

```

106 mon_ptp_T ! {16, itrDone, infos},
107     receive
108     {16, loopBack} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [loopBack]], 1,
109     ↪ 13),
109 mon_ptp_T ! {16, loopBack},
110 loop_ptp_T_16();
111     {16, rollBack} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [rollBack]], 1,
112     ↪ 13),
112 mon_ptp_T ! {16, rollBack},
113 loop_ptp_T_16();
114     {16, exitLoop} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [exitLoop]], 1,
115     ↪ 13),
115 mon_ptp_T ! {16, exitLoop}
116     end
117 .

118 %% -----
119 %% Monitor for participant ptp_T of c.p. 16

120 mon_loop_ptp_T_16() ->
121     receive
122     {16, itrDone, Info} ->
123     case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
124     true -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, mon_ptp_T_16, sel_mon_16, [rev]], 1,
125     ↪ 13),
126     _ -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, mon_ptp_T_16, sel_mon_16, [fwd]], 1, 13),
125 sel_mon_16 ! {16, rev};
126     _ -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, mon_ptp_T_16, sel_mon_16, [fwd]], 1, 13),
127 sel_mon_16 ! {16, fwd}
128     end,
129     receive
130     {16, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
131     {16, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_T_16();
132     {16, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_T_16()

133     end
134 end.

135 %% -----
136 %% Actor for participant ptp_M of c.p. 16

137 loop_ptp_M_16() ->
138     receive {15, exhReg} -> debug("[p]   p ? p : p", [15, ptp_T, ptp_M, [exhReg]], 1,
139     ↪ 13)end,
139     debug("[p]           Selector started", [14], 1, 13),
140     spawn(rgg_support, loop_sel, [14, [ptp_Ll, ptp_M], 3, 0, fwdOnly, entireIteration]),
141     receive {14, startLoop} -> debug("p starts loop p", [ptp_M, 14], debugLoop(), 13) end,
142     loop_ptp_M_14(),
143     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [10, ptp_M, ptp_Ll, [newTest]], 1, 13),
144     ptp_Ll ! {10, newTest},
145     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
146     mon_ptp_M ! {16, itrDone, infos},
147     receive
148     {16, loopBack} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [loopBack]], 1,
149     ↪ 13),
149     mon_ptp_M ! {16, loopBack},
150     loop_ptp_M_16();
151     {16, rollBack} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [rollBack]], 1,
152     ↪ 13),
152     mon_ptp_M ! {16, rollBack},
153     loop_ptp_M_16();
154     {16, exitLoop} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [exitLoop]], 1,
155     ↪ 13),
155     mon_ptp_M ! {16, exitLoop}
156     end
157 .

```

30 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

158 %% -----
159 %% Monitor for participant ptp_M of c.p. 16

160 mon_loop_ptp_M_16() ->
161     mon_loop_ptp_M_14()
162     ,
163     receive
164         {16, itrDone, Info} ->
165         case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
166             true -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, mon_ptp_M_16, sel_mon_16, [rev]], 1,
167                 ↪ 13),
168             _ -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, mon_ptp_M_16, sel_mon_16, [fwd]], 1, 13),
169         sel_mon_16 ! {16, fwd}
170     end,
171     receive
172         {16, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
173         {16, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_M_16();
174         {16, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_M_16()

175     end
176 end.

177 %% -----
178 %% Actor for participant ptp_L1 of c.p. 16

179 loop_ptp_L1_16() ->
180     receive {14, startLoop} -> debug("p starts loop p", [ptp_L1, 14], debugLoop(), 13) end,
181     loop_ptp_L1_14(),
182     receive {10, newTest} -> debug("[p]   p ? p : p", [10, ptp_M, ptp_L1, [newTest]], 1,
183         ↪ 13)end,
184     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
185     %instrumented code%
186     case rand:uniform(4) of
187         4 -> put(diff,1);
188         _ -> put(diff,0)
189     end,
190     mon_ptp_L1 ! {16, itrDone, process_info(self(),dictionary)},
191     receive
192         {16, loopBack} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [loopBack]], 1,
193             ↪ 13),
194         mon_ptp_L1 ! {16, loopBack},
195         loop_ptp_L1_16();
196         {16, rollBack} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [rollBack]], 1,
197             ↪ 13),
198         mon_ptp_L1 ! {16, rollBack},
199         loop_ptp_L1_16();
200         {16, exitLoop} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [exitLoop]], 1,
201             ↪ 13),
202         mon_ptp_L1 ! {16, exitLoop}
203     end

204 .

205 %% -----
206 %% Monitor for participant ptp_L1 of c.p. 16

207 mon_loop_ptp_L1_16() ->
208     mon_loop_ptp_L1_14()
209     ,
210     receive
211         {16, itrDone, Info} ->
212         case diff(Info) of
213             true -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [16, mon_ptp_L1_16, sel_mon_16, [rev]], 1,
214                 ↪ 13),

```

```

210 sel_mon_16 ! {16, rev};
211     _ -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [16, mon_ptp_Ll_16, sel_mon_16, [fwd]], 1,
212           ↪ 13),
212 sel_mon_16 ! {16, fwd}
213     end,
214     receive
215     {16, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
216     {16, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_Ll_16();
217     {16, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_Ll_16()

218     end
219 end.

220 %% -----
221 %% Actor for participant ptp_M of c.p. 14

222 loop_ptp_M_14() ->
223   smartReg(sel_13, spawn(rgg_support, sel_act, [], 13, [ptp_Ll, ptp_M], fun () ->
224     ↪ getBranch([13, fwdOnly, branching_table] end)), 13),
224 act_ptp_M_13()
225 ,
226   debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [14, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
227   mon_ptp_M ! {14, itrDone, infos},
228   receive
229   {14, loopBack} -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [14, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [loopBack]], 1,
230     ↪ 13),
231     mon_ptp_M ! {14, loopBack},
232     loop_ptp_M_14();
233   {14, rollBack} -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [14, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [rollBack]], 1,
234     ↪ 13),
235     mon_ptp_M ! {14, rollBack},
236     loop_ptp_M_14();
237   {14, exitLoop} -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [14, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [exitLoop]], 1,
238     ↪ 13),
239     mon_ptp_M ! {14, exitLoop}
240   end
241 .

242 %% -----
243 %% Monitor for participant ptp_M of c.p. 14

244 mon_loop_ptp_M_14() ->
245   mon_ptp_M_13()
246 ,
247   receive
248   {14, itrDone, Info} ->
249     case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
250     true -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [14, mon_ptp_M_14, sel_mon_14, [rev]], 1,
251       ↪ 13),
252     sel_mon_14 ! {14, rev};
253     _ -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [14, mon_ptp_M_14, sel_mon_14, [fwd]], 1, 13),
254     sel_mon_14 ! {14, fwd}
255     end,
256     receive
257     {14, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
258     {14, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_M_14();
259     {14, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_M_14()

260     end
261 end.

262 %% -----
263 %% Actor for participant ptp_Ll of c.p. 14

264 loop_ptp_Ll_14() ->
265   act_ptp_Ll_13()

```

32 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

262 ,
263     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [14, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
264 mon_ptp_L1 ! {14, itrDone, infos},
265     receive
266     {14, loopBack} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [14, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [loopBack]], 1,
        ↪ 13),
267 mon_ptp_L1 ! {14, loopBack},
268 loop_ptp_L1_14();
269     {14, rollBack} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [14, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [rollBack]], 1,
        ↪ 13),
270 mon_ptp_L1 ! {14, rollBack},
271 loop_ptp_L1_14();
272     {14, exitLoop} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [14, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [exitLoop]], 1,
        ↪ 13),
273 mon_ptp_L1 ! {14, exitLoop}
274     end
275 .

276 %% -----
277 %% Monitor for participant ptp_L1 of c.p. 14

278 mon_loop_ptp_L1_14() ->
279     mon_ptp_L1_13()
280 ,
281     receive
282     {14, itrDone, Info} ->
283     case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
284     true -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [14, mon_ptp_L1_14, sel_mon_14, [rev]], 1,
        ↪ 13),
285 sel_mon_14 ! {14, rev};
286     _ -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [14, mon_ptp_L1_14, sel_mon_14, [fwd]], 1,
        ↪ 13),
287 sel_mon_14 ! {14, fwd}
288     end,
289     receive
290     {14, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
291     {14, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_L1_14();
292     {14, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_L1_14()

293     end
294 end.

295 %% -----
296 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_L1 of the choice at 13

297 act_ptp_L1_13() ->
298     receive
299     {13, left} ->
300     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [left]], 1, 13),
301     mon_ptp_L1 ! {13, left},
302     receive {12, tFail} ->debug("[p]   p ? p : p", [12, ptp_M, ptp_L1, [tFail]],
        ↪ 1, 13)end;
303     {13, right} ->
304     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [right]], 1, 13),
305     mon_ptp_L1 ! {13, right},
306     receive {11, tOK} ->debug("[p]   p ? p : p", [11, ptp_M, ptp_L1, [tOK]], 1,
        ↪ 13)end
307     end,
308     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),

309     mon_ptp_L1 ! {13, exit, infos},
310     receive
311     {13, fwd} ->
312     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [fwd]], 1, 13),
313 mon_ptp_L1 ! {13, fwd};
314     {13, rev } ->

```

```

315         debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, ptp_L1, mon_ptp_L1, [rev]], 1, 13),
316 mon_ptp_L1 ! {13, rev},
317         act_ptp_L1_13()
318 end.

319 mon_ptp_L1_13() ->
320     receive
321     {13, left} ->
322         receive{13, exit, Info} -> ok end,
323         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
324     ;
325     {13, right} ->
326         receive{13, exit, Info} -> ok end,
327         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
328     end,
329 Sel = sel_mon_13,
330     case Guard of
331     true -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, mon_ptp_L1_13, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
332 Sel ! {13, rev};
333     _ -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, mon_ptp_L1_13, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
334 Sel ! {13, fwd}
335 end,
336     receive
337     {13, rev} -> mon_ptp_L1_13();
338     {13, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_L1_13
339 end.

340 %% -----
341 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_L1 of the choice at 13 done

342 %% -----
343 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_M of the choice at 13

344 act_ptp_M_13() ->
345     receive
346     {13, left} ->
347         debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [left]], 1, 13),
348         mon_ptp_M ! {13, left},
349         debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [12, ptp_M, ptp_L1, [tFail]], 1, 13),
350         case rand:uniform(10) of
351         10 ->
352             case rand:uniform(2) of
353             1 -> New = get(newbug),
354                 if New == undefined -> put(newbug,1) ;
355                 true -> put(newbug,New+1)
356             end;
357             _ -> Old = get(oldbug),
358                 if Old == undefined -> put(oldbug,1) ;
359                 true -> put(oldbug,Old+1)
360             end
361         end;
362         _ -> nobug
363     end,
364     ptp_L1 ! {12, tFail};

365     {13, right} ->
366         debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [right]], 1, 13),
367         mon_ptp_M ! {13, right},
368         debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [11, ptp_M, ptp_L1, [tOK]], 1, 13),
369         ptp_L1 ! {11, tOK}
370     end,
371     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
372 mon_ptp_M ! {13, exit, infos},
373     receive

```

34 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

374         {13, fwd} ->
375         debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [fwd]], 1, 13),
376 mon_ptp_M ! {13, fwd};
377         {13, rev } ->
378         debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [rev]], 1, 13),
379 mon_ptp_M ! {13, rev},
380         act_ptp_M_13()
381 end.

382 mon_ptp_M_13() ->
383 receive
384   {13, left} ->
385     receive{13, exit, Info} -> ok end,
386     Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
387   ;
388   {13, right} ->
389     receive{13, exit, Info} -> ok end,
390     Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
391 end,
392 Sel = sel_mon_13,
393     case Guard of
394     true -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, mon_ptp_M_13, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
395 Sel ! {13, rev};
396     _ -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [13, mon_ptp_M_13, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
397 Sel ! {13, fwd}
398 end,
399     receive
400     {13, rev} -> mon_ptp_M_13();
401     {13, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_M_13
402 end.

403 %% -----
404 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_M of the choice at 13 done

405 %% -----
406 %% Actor for participant ptp_T of c.p. 2

407 loop_ptp_T_2() ->
408 debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [21, ptp_T, ptp_M, [unitTest]], 1, 13),
409 ptp_M2 ! {21, unitTest},
410 debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [2, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
411 mon_ptp_T2 ! {2, itrDone, infos},
412 receive
413   {2, loopBack} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [2, ptp_T2, mon_ptp_T2,
414     ↪ [loopBack]], 1, 13),
415   mon_ptp_T2 ! {2, loopBack},
416   loop_ptp_T_2();
417 {2, rollBack} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [2, ptp_T2, mon_ptp_T2, [rollBack]], 1,
418     ↪ 13),
419   mon_ptp_T2 ! {2, rollBack},
420   loop_ptp_T_2();
421 {2, exitLoop} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [2, ptp_T2, mon_ptp_T2, [exitLoop]], 1,
422     ↪ 13),
423   mon_ptp_T2 ! {2, exitLoop}
424 end

425 %% -----
426 %% Monitor for participant ptp_T of c.p. 2

427 mon_loop_ptp_T_2() ->
428 receive

```

```

427         {2, itrDone, Info} ->
428         case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
429             true -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, mon_ptp_T_2, sel_mon_2, [rev]], 1, 13),
430 sel_mon_2 ! {2, rev};
431             _ -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, mon_ptp_T_2, sel_mon_2, [fwd]], 1, 13),
432 sel_mon_2 ! {2, fwd}
433         end,
434         receive
435             {2, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
436             {2, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_T_2();
437             {2, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_T_2()
438         end
439     end.

440 %% -----
441 %% Actor for participant ptp_M of c.p. 2

442 loop_ptp_M_2() ->
443     receive {21, unitTest} -> debug("[^p] ^p ? ^p : ^p", [21, ptp_T2, ptp_M2, [unitTest]],
444         ↪ 1, 13)end,
445     smartReg(sel_22, spawn(rgg_support, sel_act, [], 22, [ptp_L1, ptp_M2], fun () ->
446         ↪ getBranch([22, fwdOnly, branching_table] end)), 13),
447     act_ptp_M_22(),
448     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
449     mon_ptp_M2 ! {2, itrDone, infos},
450     receive
451         {2, loopBack} -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, ptp_M2, mon_ptp_M2,
452             ↪ [loopBack]], 1, 13),
453         mon_ptp_M2 ! {2, loopBack},
454         loop_ptp_M_2();
455     {2, rollBack} -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, ptp_M2, mon_ptp_M2, [rollBack]], 1,
456         ↪ 13),
457     mon_ptp_M2 ! {2, rollBack},
458     loop_ptp_M_2();
459     {2, exitLoop} -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, ptp_M2, mon_ptp_M2, [exitLoop]], 1,
460         ↪ 13),
461     mon_ptp_M2 ! {2, exitLoop}
462     end
463     .

464 %% -----
465 %% Monitor for participant ptp_M of c.p. 2

466 mon_loop_ptp_M_2() ->
467     mon_ptp_M_22()
468     ,
469     receive
470         {2, itrDone, Info} ->
471         case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
472             true -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, mon_ptp_M_2, sel_mon_2, [rev]], 1, 13),
473 sel_mon_2 ! {2, rev};
474             _ -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, mon_ptp_M_2, sel_mon_2, [fwd]], 1, 13),
475 sel_mon_2 ! {2, fwd}
476         end,
477         receive
478             {2, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
479             {2, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_M_2();
480             {2, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_M_2()
481         end
482     end.

483 %% -----
484 %% Actor for participant ptp_L1 of c.p. 2

```

36 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

480 loop_ptp_Ll_2() ->
481     act_ptp_Ll_22()
482 ,
483     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
484 mon_ptp_Ll ! {2, itrDone, infos},
485     receive
486     {2, loopBack} -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [loopBack]], 1,
487     ↪ 13),
487 mon_ptp_Ll ! {2, loopBack},
488 loop_ptp_Ll_2();
489     {2, rollBack} -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [rollBack]], 1,
490     ↪ 13),
490 mon_ptp_Ll ! {2, rollBack},
491 loop_ptp_Ll_2();
492     {2, exitLoop} -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [exitLoop]], 1,
493     ↪ 13),
493 mon_ptp_Ll ! {2, exitLoop}
494     end
495 .

496 %% -----
497 %% Monitor for participant ptp_Ll of c.p. 2

498 mon_loop_ptp_Ll_2() ->
499     mon_ptp_Ll_22()
500 ,
501     receive
502     {2, itrDone, Info} ->
503     case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
504     true -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, mon_ptp_Ll_2, sel_mon_2, [rev]], 1,
505     ↪ 13),
505 sel_mon_2 ! {2, rev};
506     _ -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [2, mon_ptp_Ll_2, sel_mon_2, [fwd]], 1, 13),
507 sel_mon_2 ! {2, fwd}
508     end,
509     receive
510     {2, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
511     {2, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_Ll_2();
512     {2, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_Ll_2()

513     end
514 end.

515 %% -----
516 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_Ll of the choice at 22

517 act_ptp_Ll_22() ->
518     receive
519     {22, left} ->
520     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [22, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [left]], 1, 13),
521 mon_ptp_Ll ! {22, left},
522 receive {23, tFail} -> debug("[^p] ^p ? ^p : ^p", [23, ptp_M, ptp_Ll, [tFail]], 1, 13)end;
523     {22, right} ->
524     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [22, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [right]], 1, 13),
525 mon_ptp_Ll ! {22, right},
526 receive {24, tOk} -> debug("[^p] ^p ? ^p : ^p", [24, ptp_M, ptp_Ll, [tOk]], 1, 13)end
527     end,
528     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [22, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
529 mon_ptp_Ll ! {22, exit, infos},
530     receive
531     {22, fwd} ->
532     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [22, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [fwd]], 1, 13),
533 mon_ptp_Ll ! {22, fwd};
534     {22, rev } ->
535     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [22, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [rev]], 1, 13),
536 mon_ptp_Ll ! {22, rev},

```

```

537         act_ptp_Ll_22()
538     end.

539     mon_ptp_Ll_22() ->
540         receive
541             {22, left} ->
542                 receive{22, exit, Info} -> ok end,
543                 Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
544             ;
545             {22, right} ->
546                 receive{22, exit, Info} -> ok end,
547                 Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
548         end,
549     Sel = sel_mon_22,
550     case Guard of
551     true -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [22, mon_ptp_Ll_22, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
552     Sel ! {22, rev};
553     _ -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [22, mon_ptp_Ll_22, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
554     Sel ! {22, fwd}
555 end,
556     receive
557     {22, rev} -> mon_ptp_Ll_22();
558     {22, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_Ll_22
559 end.

560 %% -----
561 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_Ll of the choice at 22 done

562 %% -----
563 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_M of the choice at 22

564     act_ptp_M_22() ->
565         receive
566             {22, left} ->
567                 debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [22, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [left]], 1, 13),
568                 mon_ptp_M ! {22, left},
569                 debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [23, ptp_M, ptp_Ll, [tFail]], 1, 13),
570                 ptp_Ll ! {23, tFail},
571                 %instrumented code%
572                 case rand:uniform(10) of
573                 10 -> put(new,1);
574                 _ -> nobug
575             end;
576             {22, right} ->
577                 debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [22, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [right]], 1, 13),
578                 mon_ptp_M ! {22, right},
579                 debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [24, ptp_M, ptp_Ll, [tOk]], 1, 13),
580                 ptp_Ll ! {24, tOk}
581             end,
582             debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [22, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
583             mon_ptp_M ! {22, exit, infos},
584             receive
585                 {22, fwd} ->
586                     debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [22, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [fwd]], 1, 13),
587                     mon_ptp_M ! {22, fwd};
588                 {22, rev } ->
589                     debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [22, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [rev]], 1, 13),
590                     mon_ptp_M ! {22, rev},
591                     act_ptp_M_22()
592             end.

593     mon_ptp_M_22() ->
594         receive
595             {22, left} ->

```

38 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

596         receive{22, exit, Info} -> ok end,
597         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
598     ;
599     {22, right} ->
600         receive{22, exit, Info} -> ok end,
601         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
602     end,
603 Sel = sel_mon_22,
604     case Guard of
605     true -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [22, mon_ptp_M_22, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
606 Sel ! {22, rev};
607     _ -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [22, mon_ptp_M_22, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
608 Sel ! {22, fwd}
609 end,
610     receive
611     {22, rev} -> mon_ptp_M_22();
612     {22, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_M_22
613 end.

614 %% -----
615 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_M of the choice at 22 done

616 %% -----
617 %% Actor for participant ptp_T of c.p. 8

618 loop_ptp_T_8() ->
619     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [7, ptp_T1, ptp_M1, [chosenTest]], 1, 13),
620     ptp_M1 ! {7, chosenTest},
621     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [8, ptp_T1, mon_ptp_T1, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
622     mon_ptp_T1 ! {8, itrDone, infos},
623     receive
624     {8, loopBack} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [8, ptp_T1, mon_ptp_T1,
625     ↪ [loopBack]], 1, 13),
626     mon_ptp_T1 ! {8, loopBack},
627     loop_ptp_T_8();
628     {8, rollBack} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [8, ptp_T1, mon_ptp_T1, [rollBack]], 1,
629     ↪ 13),
630     mon_ptp_T1 ! {8, rollBack},
631     loop_ptp_T_8();
632     {8, exitLoop} -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [8, ptp_T1, mon_ptp_T1, [exitLoop]], 1,
633     ↪ 13),
634     mon_ptp_T1 ! {8, exitLoop}
635 end
636 .

637 %% -----
638 %% Monitor for participant ptp_T of c.p. 8

639 mon_loop_ptp_T_8() ->
640     receive
641     {8, itrDone, Info} ->
642     case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
643     true -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [8, mon_ptp_T1_8, sel_mon_8, [rev]], 1,
644     ↪ 13),
645     sel_mon_8 ! {8, rev};
646     _ -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [8, mon_ptp_T1_8, sel_mon_8, [fwd]], 1, 13),
647     sel_mon_8 ! {8, fwd}
648     end,
649     receive
650     {8, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
651     {8, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_T_8();
652     {8, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_T_8()

```

```

649     end
650 end.

651 %% -----
652 %% Actor for participant ptp_M of c.p. 8

653 loop_ptp_M_8() ->
654     receive {7, chosenTest} -> debug("[~p] ~p ? ~p : ~p", [7, ptp_T1, ptp_M1, [chosenTest]],
655         ↪ 1, 13) end,
656     smartReg(sel_6, spawn(rgg_support, sel_act, [], 6, [ptp_Lg, ptp_M1], fun () ->
657         ↪ getBranch([6, fwdOnly, branching_table] end)), 13),
658     act_ptp_M_6(),
659     debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [8, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
660     mon_ptp_M1 ! {8, itrDone, infos},
661     receive
662         {8, loopBack} -> debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [8, ptp_M1, mon_ptp_M1,
663             ↪ [loopBack]], 1, 13),
664         mon_ptp_M1 ! {8, loopBack},
665         loop_ptp_M_8();
666     {8, rollBack} -> debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [8, ptp_M1, mon_ptp_M1, [rollBack]], 1,
667         ↪ 13),
668         mon_ptp_M1 ! {8, rollBack},
669         loop_ptp_M_8();
670     {8, exitLoop} -> debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [8, ptp_M1, mon_ptp_M1, [exitLoop]], 1,
671         ↪ 13),
672         mon_ptp_M1 ! {8, exitLoop}
673     end
674 .

675 %% -----
676 %% Monitor for participant ptp_M of c.p. 8

677 mon_loop_ptp_M_8() ->
678     mon_ptp_M_6(),
679     receive
680         {8, itrDone, Info} ->
681             case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
682                 true -> debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [8, mon_ptp_M_8, sel_mon_8, [rev]], 1, 13),
683                 _ -> debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [8, mon_ptp_M_8, sel_mon_8, [fwd]], 1, 13),
684             sel_mon_8 ! {8, rev};
685     sel_mon_8 ! {8, fwd}
686     end,
687     receive
688         {8, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
689         {8, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_M_8();
690         {8, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_M_8()
691     end
692 end.

693 %% -----
694 %% Actor for participant ptp_Lg of c.p. 8

695 loop_ptp_Lg_8() ->
696     act_ptp_Lg_6()
697 ,
698     debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [8, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [itrDone, infos]], 1, 13),
699     mon_ptp_Lg ! {8, itrDone, infos},
700     receive
701         {8, loopBack} -> debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [8, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [loopBack]], 1,
702             ↪ 13),
703         mon_ptp_Lg ! {8, loopBack},
704     loop_ptp_Lg_8();
705     {8, rollBack} -> debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [8, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [rollBack]], 1,
706         ↪ 13),

```

40 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

700 mon_ptp_Lg ! {8, rollBack},
701 loop_ptp_Lg_8();
702     {8, exitLoop} -> debug("[^p]  ^p ! ^p : ^p", [8, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [exitLoop]], 1,
       ↪ 13),
703 mon_ptp_Lg ! {8, exitLoop}
704     end
705 .

706 %% -----
707 %% Monitor for participant ptp_Lg of c.p. 8

708 mon_loop_ptp_Lg_8() ->
709     mon_ptp_Lg_6()
710 ,
711     receive
712         {8, itrDone, Info} ->
713         case checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly) of
714             true -> debug("[^p]  ^p ! ^p : ^p", [8, mon_ptp_Lg_8, sel_mon_8, [rev]], 1,
       ↪ 13),
715 sel_mon_8 ! {8, rev};
716             _ -> debug("[^p]  ^p ! ^p : ^p", [8, mon_ptp_Lg_8, sel_mon_8, [fwd]], 1, 13),
717 sel_mon_8 ! {8, fwd}
718         end,
719         receive
720             {8, exitLoop} -> loopDone;
721             {8, loopBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_Lg_8();
722             {8, rollBack} -> mon_loop_ptp_Lg_8()

723     end
724 end.

725 %% -----
726 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_Lg of the choice at 6

727 act_ptp_Lg_6() ->
728     receive
729         {6, left} ->
730         debug("[^p]  ^p ! ^p : ^p", [6, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [left]], 1, 13),
731 mon_ptp_Lg ! {6, left},
732 receive {5, new} ->debug("[^p]  ^p ? ^p : ^p", [5, ptp_M1, ptp_Lg, [new]], 1, 13)end;
733         {6, right} ->
734         debug("[^p]  ^p ! ^p : ^p", [6, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [right]], 1, 13),
735 mon_ptp_Lg ! {6, right},
736 receive {3, stable} ->debug("[^p]  ^p ? ^p : ^p", [3, ptp_M1, ptp_Lg, [stable]], 1, 13)end
737     end,
738     debug("[^p]  ^p ! ^p : ^p", [6, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
739 mon_ptp_Lg ! {6, exit, infos},
740     receive
741         {6, fwd} ->
742         debug("[^p]  ^p ! ^p : ^p", [6, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [fwd]], 1, 13),
743 mon_ptp_Lg ! {6, fwd};
744         {6, rev } ->
745         debug("[^p]  ^p ! ^p : ^p", [6, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [rev]], 1, 13),
746 mon_ptp_Lg ! {6, rev},
747         act_ptp_Lg_6()
748     end.

749 mon_ptp_Lg_6() ->
750     receive
751         {6, left} ->
752         receive{6, exit, Info} -> ok end,
753         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
754     ;
755         {6, right} ->
756         receive{6, exit, Info} -> ok end,
757         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)

```

```

758     end,
759 Sel = sel_mon_6,
760     case Guard of
761     true -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [6, mon_ptp_Lg_6, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
762 Sel ! {6, rev};
763     _ -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [6, mon_ptp_Lg_6, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
764 Sel ! {6, fwd}
765 end,
766     receive
767     {6, rev} -> mon_ptp_Lg_6();
768     {6, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_Lg_6
769 end.

770 %% -----
771 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_Lg of the choice at 6 done

772 %% -----
773 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_M of the choice at 6

774 act_ptp_M_6() ->
775     receive
776     {6, left} ->
777         debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [6, ptp_M1, mon_ptp_M1, [left]], 1, 13),
778         mon_ptp_M1 ! {6, left},
779         debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [5, ptp_M1, ptp_Lg, [new]], 1, 13),
780         ptp_Lg ! {5, new};
781     {6, right} ->
782         debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [6, ptp_M1, mon_ptp_M1, [right]], 1, 13),
783         mon_ptp_M1 ! {6, right},
784         debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [3, ptp_M1, ptp_Lg, [stable]], 1, 13),
785         ptp_Lg ! {3, stable}
786     end,
787     debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [6, ptp_M1, mon_ptp_M1, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
788     mon_ptp_M1 ! {6, exit, infos},
789     receive
790     {6, fwd} ->
791         debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [6, ptp_M1, mon_ptp_M1, [fwd]], 1, 13),
792         mon_ptp_M1 ! {6, fwd};
793     {6, rev } ->
794         debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [6, ptp_M1, mon_ptp_M1, [rev]], 1, 13),
795         mon_ptp_M1 ! {6, rev},
796         act_ptp_M_6()
797 end.

798 mon_ptp_M_6() ->
799     receive
800     {6, left} ->
801         receive{6, exit, Info} -> ok end,
802         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
803     ;
804     {6, right} ->
805         receive{6, exit, Info} -> ok end,
806         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
807     end,
808 Sel = sel_mon_6,
809     case Guard of
810     true -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [6, mon_ptp_M_6, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
811 Sel ! {6, rev};
812     _ -> debug("[p]   ~p ! ~p : ~p", [6, mon_ptp_M_6, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
813 Sel ! {6, fwd}
814 end,
815     receive
816     {6, rev} -> mon_ptp_M_6();
817     {6, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_M_6

```

42 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

818         end.

819 %% -----
820 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_M of the choice at 6 done

821 %% -----
822 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_Lg of the choice at 17

823 act_ptp_Lg_17() ->
824     receive
825     {17, left} ->
826         debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [left]], 1, 13),
827 mon_ptp_Lg ! {17, left};
828     {17, right} ->
829         debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [right]], 1, 13),
830 mon_ptp_Lg ! {17, right},
831     receive {8, startLoop} -> debug("~p starts loop ~p", [ptp_Lg, 8], debugLoop(), 13) end,
832     loop_ptp_Lg_8()
833     end,
834     debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
835 mon_ptp_Lg ! {17, exit, infos},
836     receive
837     {17, fwd} ->
838         debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [fwd]], 1, 13),
839 mon_ptp_Lg ! {17, fwd};
840     {17, rev } ->
841         debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, ptp_Lg, mon_ptp_Lg, [rev]], 1, 13),
842 mon_ptp_Lg ! {17, rev},
843     act_ptp_Lg_17()
844     end.

845 mon_ptp_Lg_17() ->
846     receive
847     {17, left} ->
848         receive{17, exit, Info} -> ok end,
849         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
850     ;
851     {17, right} ->
852         mon_loop_ptp_Lg_8()
853     ,
854         receive{17, exit, Info} -> ok end,
855         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
856     end,
857     Sel = sel_mon_17,
858     case Guard of
859     true -> debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, mon_ptp_Lg_17, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
860     Sel ! {17, rev};
861     _ -> debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, mon_ptp_Lg_17, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
862     Sel ! {17, fwd}
863     end,
864     receive
865     {17, rev} -> mon_ptp_Lg_17();
866     {17, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_Lg_17
867     end.

868 %% -----
869 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_Lg of the choice at 17 done

870 %% -----
871 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_Ll of the choice at 17

```

```

872 act_ptp_Ll_17() ->
873     receive
874         {17, left} ->
875             debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [17, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [left]], 1, 13),
876     mon_ptp_Ll ! {17, left},
877     receive {16, startLoop} -> debug("p starts loop p", [ptp_Ll, 16], debugLoop(), 13) end,
878     loop_ptp_Ll_16();
879         {17, right} ->
880             debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [17, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [right]], 1, 13),
881     mon_ptp_Ll ! {17, right},
882     receive {2, startLoop} -> debug("p starts loop p", [ptp_Ll, 2], debugLoop(), 13) end,
883     loop_ptp_Ll_2()
884     end,
885     debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [17, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
886     mon_ptp_Ll ! {17, exit, infos},
887     receive
888         {17, fwd} ->
889             debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [17, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [fwd]], 1, 13),
890     mon_ptp_Ll ! {17, fwd};
891         {17, rev } ->
892             debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [17, ptp_Ll, mon_ptp_Ll, [rev]], 1, 13),
893     mon_ptp_Ll ! {17, rev},
894     act_ptp_Ll_17()
895     end.

896 mon_ptp_Ll_17() ->
897     receive
898         {17, left} ->
899             mon_loop_ptp_Ll_16()
900     ,
901         receive{17, exit, Info} -> ok end,
902         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
903     ;
904     {17, right} ->
905         mon_loop_ptp_Ll_2()
906     ,
907         receive{17, exit, Info} -> ok end,
908         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
909     end,
910     Sel = sel_mon_17,
911     case Guard of
912     true -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [17, mon_ptp_Ll_17, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
913     Sel ! {17, rev};
914     _ -> debug("[p]   p ! p : p", [17, mon_ptp_Ll_17, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
915     Sel ! {17, fwd}
916     end,
917     receive
918         {17, rev} -> mon_ptp_Ll_17();
919         {17, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_Ll_17
920     end.

921 %% -----
922 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_Ll of the choice at 17 done

923 %% -----
924 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_M of the choice at 17

925 act_ptp_M2_9() ->
926     receive {2, startLoop} -> debug("p starts loop p", [ptp_M2, 2], debugLoop(), 13) end,
927     loop_ptp_M2(),
928     ptp_M!{9,done}
929     .

```

44 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

930 act_ptp_M1_9() ->
931     receive {8, startLoop} -> debug("~p starts loop ~p", [ptp_M1, 8], debugLoop(), 13) end,
932     loop_ptp_M_8(),
933     ptp_M!{9,done}
934 .

935 act_ptp_M17() ->
936     receive
937         {17, left} ->
938             debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [left]], 1, 13),
939             mon_ptp_M ! {17, left},
940             receive {16, startLoop} -> debug("~p starts loop ~p", [ptp_M, 16],
941                 ↪ debugLoop(), 13) end,
942             loop_ptp_M16();
943         {17, right} ->
944             debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [right]], 1, 13),
945             mon_ptp_M ! {17, right},
946             %parallel%
947             smartReg(ptp_M1, spawn(code_gen,act_ptp_M1_9, [],1),
948             smartReg(ptp_M2, spawn(code_gen,act_ptp_M2_9, [],1),
949             lists:foreach(
950                 fun(_) ->
951                     receive{9,done} -> join end
952                 end,
953                 [ptp_M1,ptp_M2]
954             ),
955             io:format("threads of M done .....\\n")
956     end,
957     debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
958     %instrumented code
959     mon_ptp_M ! {17, exit, process_info(self(),dictionary)},
960     receive
961         {17, fwd} ->
962             debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [fwd]], 1, 13),
963             mon_ptp_M ! {17, fwd};
964         {17, rev } ->
965             debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, ptp_M, mon_ptp_M, [rev]], 1, 13),
966             mon_ptp_M ! {17, rev},
967             act_ptp_M17()
968 end.

969 mon_ptp_M2_9() ->
970     mon_loop_ptp_M_2(),
971     mon_ptp_M!{9,done}
972 .

973 mon_ptp_M1_9() ->
974     mon_loop_ptp_M_8(),
975     mon_ptp_M!{9,done}
976 .

977 mon_ptp_M17() ->
978     receive
979         {17, left} ->
980             mon_loop_ptp_M16()
981     ,
982     receive{17, exit, Info} -> ok end,
983     %Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
984     Guard = check_ratio(Info)

985 ;
986 {17, right} ->
987 %parallel%
988 smartReg(mon_ptp_M1, spawn(code_gen,mon_ptp_M1_9, [],1),
989 smartReg(mon_ptp_M2, spawn(code_gen,mon_ptp_M2_9, [],1),
990 lists:foreach(
991     fun(_) ->
992         receive{9,done} -> join end

```

```

992         end,
993         [ptp_M1,ptp_M2]
994     ),

995     receive{17, exit, Info} -> ok end,
996     %Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
997     Guard = new_bug(Info)
998 end,
999 Sel = sel_mon_17,
1000 case Guard of
1001 true -> debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, mon_ptp_M_17, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
1002 Sel ! {17, rev};
1003 _ -> debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, mon_ptp_M_17, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
1004 Sel ! {17, fwd}
1005 end,
1006 receive
1007 {17, rev} -> mon_ptp_M_17();
1008 {17, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_M_17
1009 end.

1010 %% -----
1011 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_M of the choice at 17 done

1012 %% -----
1013 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_T of the choice at 17

1014 act_ptp_T2_9() ->
1015 debug("[~p] Selector started", [2], 1, 13),
1016 spawn(rgg_support,loop_sel,[2, [ptp_L1, ptp_M2, ptp_T2], 3, 0, fwdOnly,
1017     ↪ entireIteration]),
1018 receive {2, startLoop} -> debug("~p starts loop ~p", [ptp_T2, 2], debugLoop(), 13) end,
1019 loop_ptp_T_2(),
1020 ptp_T!{9,done}
1021 .

1022 act_ptp_T1_9() ->
1023 debug("[~p] Selector started", [8], 1, 13),
1024 spawn(rgg_support,loop_sel,[8, [ptp_Lg, ptp_M1, ptp_T1], 3, 0, fwdOnly,
1025     ↪ entireIteration]),
1026 receive {8, startLoop} -> debug("~p starts loop ~p", [ptp_T1, 8], debugLoop(), 13) end,
1027 loop_ptp_T_8(),
1028 ptp_T!{9,done}
1029 .

1030 act_ptp_T_17() ->
1031 receive
1032 {17, left} ->
1033 debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [left]], 1, 13),
1034 mon_ptp_T ! {17, left},
1035 debug("[~p] Selector started", [16], 1, 13),
1036 spawn(rgg_support,loop_sel,[16, [ptp_L1, ptp_M, ptp_T], 3, 0, fwdOnly,
1037     ↪ entireIteration]),
1038 receive {16, startLoop} -> debug("~p starts loop ~p", [ptp_T, 16], debugLoop(),
1039     ↪ 13) end,
1040 loop_ptp_T_16();
1041 {17, right} ->
1042 debug("[~p] ~p ! ~p : ~p", [17, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [right]], 1, 13),
1043 mon_ptp_T ! {17, right},
1044 smartReg(pty_T1, spawn(code_gen,act_ptp_T1_9, [],1),
1045 smartReg(pty_T2, spawn(code_gen,act_ptp_T2_9, [],1),
1046 lists:foreach(
1047 fun(_) ->
1048 receive{9,done} -> join end
1049 end,

```

```

1046         [ptp_T1,ptp_T2]
1047     )
1048     end,
1049     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [17, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [exit, infos]], 1, 13),
1050 mon_ptp_T ! {17, exit, infos},
1051 receive
1052     {17, fwd} ->
1053     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [17, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [fwd]], 1, 13),
1054 mon_ptp_T ! {17, fwd};
1055     {17, rev } ->
1056     debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [17, ptp_T, mon_ptp_T, [rev]], 1, 13),
1057 mon_ptp_T ! {17, rev},
1058     act_ptp_T_17()
1059 end.

1060 mon_ptp_T2_9() ->
1061     mon_loop_ptp_T_2(),
1062     mon_ptp_T!{9,done},
1063     io:format("thread monitor ^p done \n",["T2"])

1064 .

1065 mon_ptp_T1_9() ->
1066     mon_loop_ptp_T_8(),
1067     io:format("thread monitor ^p done \n",["T1"]),
1068     mon_ptp_T!{9,done}
1069 .

1070 mon_ptp_T_17() ->
1071     receive
1072     {17, left} ->
1073         mon_loop_ptp_T_16()
1074     ,
1075         receive{17, exit, Info} -> ok end,
1076         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
1077     ;
1078     {17, right} ->
1079         smartReg(mon_ptp_T1, spawn(code_gen,mon_ptp_T1_9, [],1),
1080         smartReg(mon_ptp_T2, spawn(code_gen,mon_ptp_T2_9, [],1),
1081         lists:foreach(
1082             fun(_) ->
1083                 receive{9,done} -> join end
1084             end,
1085             [ptp_T1,ptp_T2]
1086         ),
1087         receive{17, exit, Info} -> ok end,
1088         Guard = checkGuard(guard, Info, fwdOnly)
1089     end,
1090 Sel = sel_mon_17,
1091     case Guard of
1092     true -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [17, mon_ptp_T_17, Sel, [rev]], 1, 13),
1093 Sel ! {17, rev};
1094     _ -> debug("[^p] ^p ! ^p : ^p", [17, mon_ptp_T_17, Sel, [fwd]], 1, 13),
1095 Sel ! {17, fwd}
1096 end,
1097     receive
1098     {17, rev} -> mon_ptp_T_17();
1099     {17, fwd} -> done_mon_ptp_T_17
1100 end.

1101 %reversion guards for L1
1102 diff(Info) ->
1103     {_, Status} = Info,
1104     L = lists:filter(fun(X) -> case X of {diff,_} -> true ; _ -> false end end, Status),
1105     case L of
1106     [0] -> false ;

```

```

1107     _ -> true
1108     end
1109     .

1110 %reversion guards for M%
1111 new_bug(Info) ->
1112     {_, Status} = Info,
1113     L = lists:filter(fun(X) -> case X of {bug,_} -> true ; _ -> false end end, Status),
1114     case L of
1115     [] -> true ;
1116     _ -> false
1117     end
1118     .

1119 check_ratio(Info) ->
1120     Threshold = 2,
1121     {_, Status} = Info,
1122     N = lists:filter(fun(X) -> case X of {newbug,_} -> true ; _ -> false end end, Status),
1123     O = lists:filter(fun(X) -> case X of {oldbug,_} -> true ; _ -> false end end, Status),
1124     case {N,O} of
1125     {[],[ ]} -> false;
1126     {[],[T]} -> false;
1127     {[T],[ ]} -> false;
1128     {_,_} -> [{_,Old}] = O, [{_,New}] = N,
1129             New / New + Old > Threshold
1130     end.

1131 %% -----
1132 %% Actor and monitor for participant ptp_T of the choice at 17 done

1133 mon_ptp_D_fun() -> receive go -> emptyMonitor end.
1134 ptp_D_fun() -> receive {go,Pid} -> receive {20, code} -> debug("[p] p ? p : p",
1135     ↪ [20, ptp_R, ptp_D, [code]], 1, 13)end,
1136     debug("[p] p ! p : p", [19, ptp_D, ptp_R, [pullReq]], 1, 13),
1137     ptp_R ! {19, pullReq}, Pid ! done_actor end
1138     .
1139 mon_ptp_Lg_fun() -> receive go -> going end,
1140 mon_ptp_Lg_17()
1141     .

1142 ptp_Lg_fun() -> receive {go,Pid} ->act_ptp_Lg_17()
1143     , Pid ! done_actor end
1144     .
1145 mon_ptp_Ll_fun() -> receive go -> going end,
1146 mon_ptp_Ll_17()
1147     .

1148 ptp_Ll_fun() -> receive {go,Pid} ->act_ptp_Ll_17()
1149     , Pid ! done_actor end
1150     .
1151 mon_ptp_M_fun() -> receive go -> going end,
1152 mon_ptp_M_17()
1153     .

1154 ptp_M_fun() -> receive {go,Pid} ->act_ptp_M_17()
1155     , Pid ! done_actor end
1156     .
1157 mon_ptp_R_fun() -> receive go -> emptyMonitor end.
1158 ptp_R_fun() -> receive {go,Pid} -> debug("[p] p ! p : p", [20, ptp_R, ptp_D, [code]],
1159     ↪ 1, 13),
1160     ptp_D ! {20, code},
1161     receive {19, pullReq} -> debug("[p] p ? p : p", [19, ptp_D, ptp_R, [pullReq]],
1162     ↪ 1, 13)end,
1163     debug("[p] p ! p : p", [18, ptp_R, ptp_T, [startTesting]], 1, 13),
1164     ptp_T ! {18, startTesting}, Pid ! done_actor end
1165     .
1166 mon_ptp_T_fun() -> receive go -> going end,

```

48 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

1164 mon_ptp_T_17()
1165 .

1166 ptp_T_fun() -> receive {go,Pid} -> receive {18, startTesting} -> debug("[`p]  `p ? `p
    ↳ : `p", [18, ptp_R, ptp_T, [startTesting]], 1, 13)end,
1167 smartReg(sel_17, spawn(rgg_support, sel_act, [[], 17, [ptp_Lg, ptp_Ll, ptp_M, ptp_T], fun () ->
    ↳ getBranch([17, fwdOnly, branching_table]) end)), 13),
1168 act_ptp_T_17()
1169 , Pid ! done_actor end
1170 .
1171 main() ->
1172     case lists:member(branching_table, ets:all()) of
1173     true -> ets:delete(branching_table);
1174     _ -> noTable
1175     end,
1176     ets:new(branching_table, [set, named_table, public]),
1177     ets:insert(branching_table, {8, 1}),
1178     ets:insert(branching_table, {6, 1}),
1179     ets:insert(branching_table, {22, 1}),
1180     ets:insert(branching_table, {2, 1}),
1181     ets:insert(branching_table, {17, 1}),
1182     ets:insert(branching_table, {16, 3}),
1183     ets:insert(branching_table, {14, 3}),
1184     ets:insert(branching_table, {13, 2}),
1185     ets:insert(branching_table, {debug, 13}),
1186     smartReg(mon_ptp_D, spawn(code_gen, mon_ptp_D_fun, [], 13),
1187     smartReg(pty_D, spawn(code_gen, ptp_D_fun, [], 13),
1188     smartReg(mon_ptp_Lg, spawn(code_gen, mon_ptp_Lg_fun, [], 13),
1189     smartReg(pty_Lg, spawn(code_gen, ptp_Lg_fun, [], 13),
1190     smartReg(mon_ptp_Ll, spawn(code_gen, mon_ptp_Ll_fun, [], 13),
1191     smartReg(pty_Ll, spawn(code_gen, ptp_Ll_fun, [], 13),
1192     smartReg(mon_ptp_M, spawn(code_gen, mon_ptp_M_fun, [], 13),
1193     smartReg(pty_M, spawn(code_gen, ptp_M_fun, [], 13),
1194     smartReg(mon_ptp_R, spawn(code_gen, mon_ptp_R_fun, [], 13),
1195     smartReg(pty_R, spawn(code_gen, ptp_R_fun, [], 13),
1196     smartReg(mon_ptp_T, spawn(code_gen, mon_ptp_T_fun, [], 13),
1197     smartReg(pty_T, spawn(code_gen, ptp_T_fun, [], 13),
1198     STime = os:system_time(), ptp_D ! {go, self()},
1199     mon_ptp_D ! go,
1200     ptp_Lg ! {go, self()},
1201     mon_ptp_Lg ! go,
1202     ptp_Ll ! {go, self()},
1203     mon_ptp_Ll ! go,
1204     ptp_M ! {go, self()},
1205     mon_ptp_M ! go,
1206     ptp_R ! {go, self()},
1207     mon_ptp_R ! go,
1208     ptp_T ! {go, self()},
1209     mon_ptp_T ! go,
1210     receive done_actor -> ok end,
1211     receive done_actor -> ok end,
1212     receive done_actor -> ok end,
1213     receive done_actor -> ok end,
1214     receive done_actor -> ok end,
1215     receive done_actor -> ok end,
1216     file:write_file(".time.tmp", integer_to_list(os:system_time() - STime))
1217     .

```

A.3 Supporting Functions

Supporting functions module. This module contains run time functions necessary to execute the examples.

```

1  -module(rgg_support).
2  -import(lists, [foreach/2]).
3  -export([
4      lookup/2,
5      debug/3,
6      debug/4,
7      debugLoop/0,
8      smartReg/3,
9      smartUnreg/1,
10     notify/3,
11     getBranch/1,
12     getBranch/2,
13     loop_sel/6,
14     sel_act/4,
15     sel_mon/3,
16     loop_entry/6,
17     rb/6,
18     lb/6,
19     el/2
20     ]).

21  %% ----- Auxiliary function -----

22  start_monitor(CP, P, Fun) ->
23      put(debug, get(debug)),
24      MonName = list_to_atom("sel_mon_" ++ integer_to_list(CP)),
25      Proc = spawn(rgg_support, Fun, [CP, P, self()]),
26      smartReg(MonName, Proc, get(debug))
27  .

28  lookup(Rnd, CP) ->
29      [{_,V}] = lists:filter(fun({CP1,_}) -> CP == CP1 end, Rnd),
30      V
31  .

32  %% set debugRegistration() lower than debug() if you want debugging messages
33  debugRegistration() -> 7
34  .

35  %% set debugLoop() lower than debug() if you want debugging messages
36  debugLoop() -> 5
37  .

38  %% set debugRev() lower than debug() if you want debugging messages
39  %% debugRev() -> 5
40  %% .

41  %% Note that the debug function behaves as a normal
42  %% print if Level is strictly negative
43  debug(Fmt, Params, Level) ->
44      debug(Fmt, Params, Level, get(debug))
45  .

46  debug(Fmt, Params, Level, Debug) ->
47      case Debug >= Level of
48          true -> io:format(":\t " ++ Fmt ++ "\n", Params);
49          false -> ""
50      end
51  .

```

```

52 smartReg(Pname, Proc, Debug) ->
53     case lists:member(Pname, registered()) of
54         true -> debug("smartReg: ~p registered already", [Pname], debugRegistration(), Debug),
55                smartReg(Pname, Proc, Debug);
56         _    -> register(Pname, Proc)
57     end,
58     debug("smartReg: ~p started", [Pname], 1, Debug),
59     debug("smartReg: now ~p has been registered", [Pname], debugRegistration(), Debug)
60 .

61 smartUnreg(Pname) ->
62     debug("smartUnreg: Unregistering ~p", [Pname], debugRegistration()),
63     case lists:member(Pname, registered()) of
64         true -> unregister(Pname);
65         _    -> smartUnreg(Pname)
66     end,
67     debug("smartUnreg: now ~p has been unregistered", [Pname], debugRegistration())
68 .

69 notify(CP, M, P) ->
70     [{_, DB}] = ets:lookup(branching_table, debug),
71     foreach(
72         fun(X) ->
73             debug("[~p] \t Selector ! ~p: " ++ atom_to_list(M), [CP, X], 1, DB),
74             X ! {CP, M}
75         end,
76         P
77     )
78 .

79 getBranch(Param, bra) ->
80     CP = lists:nth(1, Param),
81     Table = lists:nth(2, Param),
82     [{_, V}] = ets:lookup(Table, CP),
83     io:format(" ---> ~p\n", [V]),
84     list_to_atom("branch_" ++ integer_to_list(V))
85 .

86 getBranch(Param) ->
87     case Param of
88         [] -> case rand:uniform(2) of
89                 1 -> left;
90                 2 -> right
91             end;
92         _ -> CP = lists:nth(1, Param),
93                Mode = lists:nth(2, Param),
94                Table = lists:nth(3, Param),
95                [{_, V}] = ets:lookup(Table, CP),
96                case V of
97                    1 -> case Mode of mimic -> right; _ -> left end;
98                    2 -> case Mode of mimic -> left ; _ -> right end
99                end
100     end
101 .

102 loop_entry(CP, P, V, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod) ->
103     %% waiting aggregated decision from the selector's monitor
104     %% note that in the simulation the value of the decision is immaterial
105     [{_, Rounds}] = ets:lookup(branching_table, CP),
106
107     Itr = Rounds - V,
108     %% Get the aggregated outcome from the monitor of the selector
109     case Mod of
110         mimic ->
111             %% fetching loop modality set by experiments:testLoop
112             case LoopMod of

```

```

113         stuttering ->
114             receive {CP, _} ->
115                 case RollBack > Itr of
116                     true ->
117                         start_monitor(CP, P, sel_mon),
118                         lb(CP, P, V, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod);           % The current
119     ↪ execution of the loop is at an iteration preceding the last rollback, hence it should not be
120     ↪ roll-backed
119         _ -> case {RollBack /= Rounds, V > 0} of
120             {true, _} ->
121                 start_monitor(CP, P, sel_mon),
122                 rb(CP, P, Rounds, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod);
123             {false, true} ->
124                 start_monitor(CP, P, sel_mon),
125                 lb(CP, P, V, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod);
126             {false, false} -> el(CP, P)
127         end
128     end
129 end;
130 currentIteration ->
131     %% At the end of the execution in this semantics
132     %% the following equations hold
133     %% Rounds == number of loopBack == number of rollBack messages
134     receive {CP, _} ->
135         case RollBack == Itr + 1 of
136             true -> case V > 0 of
137                 true ->
138                     start_monitor(CP, P, sel_mon),
139                     lb(CP, P, V, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod);
140                 _ -> el(CP, P)
141             end;
142             _ ->
143                 start_monitor(CP, P, sel_mon),
144                 rb(CP, P, V, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod)
145         end
146     end;
147 entireIteration ->
148     [{_, OV}] = ets:lookup(branching_table, CP),
149     case {V == 0, RollBack} of
150         {true, 0} ->
151             %% monitor should be already on: TODO: it shouldn't
152             notify(CP, endIteration, P),
153             receive {CP, _} -> rb(CP, P, OV, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod) end;
154         {true, 1} ->
155             start_monitor(CP, P, sel_mon),
156             notify(CP, endIteration, P),
157             receive {CP, _} -> el(CP, P) end;
158         {true, _} -> whatTHE;
159         {_, _} -> lb(CP, P, V, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod)
160     end
161 end;
162 fwdOnly -> receive {CP, _} ->
163     case V == 0 of
164         true -> el(CP, P);
165         _ -> start_monitor(CP, P, sel_mon),
166             lb(CP, P, V, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod)
167     end
168 end;
169 _ -> case V == 0 of
170     true -> el(CP, P);
171     _ -> lb(CP, P, V, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod)
172 end
173 %% It does not make sense to reverse an end-loop if V>0 when using the forward-only
174     ↪ semantics
175 .
176 rb(CP, P, V, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod) ->
    
```

52 Authors Suppressed Due to Excessive Length

```

177     notify(CP, rollBack, P ),
178     loop_entry(CP, P, V, RollBack + 1, Mod, LoopMod)
179 .

180 lb(CP, P, V, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod) ->
181     case {Mod, LoopMod} of
182         {fwdOnly, _} -> notify(CP, loopBack, P);
183         {_, entireIteration} -> notify(CP, loopBack, P);
184         {_, _} -> notify(CP, loopBack, P)
185     end,
186     loop_entry(CP, P, V - 1, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod)
187 .

188 el(CP, P) ->
189     notify(CP, exitLoop, P ),
190     debug("exiting `p", [CP], debugLoop())
191 .

192 %% ----- Actors and monitors -----

193 loop_sel(CP, P, V, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod) ->
194     %before loop_mon
195     start_monitor(CP, P, sel_mon),                % starting monitor
196     %%
197     %% V >= 0 otherwise the loop is infinite
198     %%
199     notify(CP, startLoop, P),
200     loop_entry(CP, P, V, RollBack, Mod, LoopMod)
201 .

202 sel_act(Attempt, CP, P, GetBranch) ->
203     start_monitor(CP, P, sel_mon),
204     %% determine selection left or right
205     Sel =
206         case Attempt of
207             [] -> GetBranch();
208             [left] -> right;
209             [right] -> left;
210             _ -> throw("panic: no more branches available. Totally unexpected: this is REALLY
                ↪ ODD!!!")
211         end,
212     % send the selection to each participant
213     notify(CP, Sel, P),
214     %% receive the outcome from the Selector Monitor and decide the fate of the branch
215     receive {CP, Outcome} ->
216         Decision =
217             case {Outcome, Attempt} of
218                 {fwd, _} -> fwd;
219                 {rev, []} -> rev;
220                 {_, _} -> fwd
221             end
222         end,
223     notify(CP, Decision, P),
224     %% foreach(fun(X) -> debug("[`p] \t Selector ! `p :`p\n", [CP, X, Sel], 1), X ! {CP,
225     ↪ Decision} end, P),
226     case Decision of
227         rev -> sel_act(Attempt ++ [Sel], CP, P, GetBranch);
228         _ -> end_branch
229     end
230 .

230 sel_mon(CP, Ptps, Selector) ->
231     %% receives the messages from all the monitors of the participants
232     %% Ptps. If one of them is to reverse the loop then 'rev' is sent
233     %% to 'Selector' Note that this monitor is ephemeral

```

```
234   %%
235   MsgList = lists:map(fun(_) -> receive {CP, M} -> M end end, Ptps),
236   Msg = case lists:member(rev, MsgList) of
237     true -> rev;
238     _    -> fwd
239   end,
240   debug("[^p] \t Monitor ! Selector: ^p", [CP, Msg], 1, get(debug)),
241   Selector!{CP, Msg},
242   debug("[^p] \t Monitor done", [CP], 1, get(debug))
243 .
```